

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Dutch national newspaper depictions of mental health: the impact of framing on mental health stigma

Borah Spoorenberg

Date of submission: 18th of August, 2023

Internship organization: Science Communication and Society, Leiden University

SCS-supervisor: Julie Schoorl

Corresponding author: Borah Spoorenberg.

Email: borah.spoorenberg@gmail.com

Abstract

With the COVID-19 pandemic as a catalyst, mental health conditions have been increasing in the Netherlands. Due to low levels of mental health literacy and persistent negative attitudes towards mental health, those experiencing a mental illness often refrain from seeking psychological treatment. Newspaper portrayals of mental health have previously been recognized to foster misleading beliefs, thereby lowering public mental health literacy and perpetuating stigmatization. To our knowledge, we are the first to explore the current stance of Dutch newspapers on mental health. Content analysis was performed on 120 mental health-related news articles that were published in five Dutch national newspapers over 10 weeks in 2022. While mental health tended to be tainted by violence, Dutch newspapers portrayed mental health more positively relative to printed media elsewhere with regards to causes of mental illnesses, quotations and mental health interventions. Dutch popular newspapers tended to incorporate less destigmatizing elements compared to quality newspapers. News articles founded on scientific news triggers were likely to convey objective mental health-related information, while those founded on non-scientific news triggers were more likely to apply a human interest frame by which those with mental illnesses are humanized. Symptomatology of depression, anxiety disorder and burn-out was overlapping in news articles, thus impairing correct recognition of these disorders among readers. Tailored guidelines for journalists are needed to improve their mental health literacy and to decrease their stigmatizing attitudes. Dutch newspapers can then present themselves as a vehicle that increases the willingness to seek psychological help among the population.

Introduction

Mental health has been steadily declining over the last decades on a global level (Richter et al., 2019). In 2019, an estimated 1 in every 8 people lived with a mental disorder (World Health Organization, 2019b). The World Health Organization (WHO) postulates mental health as “a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community” (World Health Organization, 2004, p. 10). A mental disorder, typically used interchangeably with mental illness or mental health condition, is characterized by “a clinically significant disturbance in an individual’s cognition, emotional regulation, or behavior” (World Health Organization, 2019b). These disturbances interfere with daily life in such a manner that treatment is required.

Since the beginning of 2020, the COVID-19 outbreak has likely deteriorated the mental health of the global population further as quarantine and consequent loss of freedom, boredom, loneliness and uncertainty can have detrimental impacts on one’s mental wellbeing (Brooks et al., 2020). Timely research has reported exacerbated psychological distress due to the COVID-19 pandemic among adults in the USA, UK, Denmark and China (McGinty et al., 2020; Pierce et al., 2020; Sønderskov et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020). Due to the pandemic, WHO estimated a staggering 25% increase in the prevalence of mental health illnesses among the global population. In line with this speculated rise, a recent report approximates 1 in 5 adults dealing with mental health conditions in the USA as of 2022 (Mental Health America, 2022).

The impact of mental health literacy and stigma on professional help-seeking

In light of the overwhelming prevalence of mental health conditions in present day, providing correct knowledge on mental health, illness and professional treatment is deemed crucial to improve mental health literacy among the general public. As first defined by Jorm et al. (1997), mental health literacy involves “the knowledge and beliefs about mental disorders which aid their recognition, management or prevention”. Previously it has been indicated that a higher mental health literacy level corresponds to an increasingly positive attitude towards help-seeking (Jung et al., 2017; Milin et al., 2016). Furthermore, a better knowledge regarding symptomatology of a mental health condition aids in recognizing a mental disease and in communicating clearly with health practitioners to receive help, thereby hampering further deterioration of public mental health (Jorm, 2000).

However, despite the need to receive help, up to 75% of those experiencing a mental health condition refrain from seeking professional treatment (World Health Organization, 2020). Aside from a lack of mental healthcare services, mental health-related stigma and consequent fear of negative labelling can be regarded as a prominent individual barrier for help-seeking (Gaebel et al., 2017). Stigma around mental illnesses treatment has been present for centuries. Recorded documents go as far back as ancient Greece, where people were believed to develop mental disorders as a result of being inflicted with *divine madness*. Greek Gods would penetrate their madness in the human body as a punishment to those who disrespect the deities (Encarnación Villalba Babiloni, 2016). The perception of the mentally ill as madmen was continued with the witches’ mass execution in the Middle Ages that is thought to have been a persecution of those with mental illnesses, and up to the Nazi reign in Germany during which people with psychiatric mental illnesses were murdered (Rössler, 2016). Even to this day, there exists a persistent negative attitude towards mental health in mankind (Gaebel et al., 2017).

Goffman firstly coined the term ‘stigma’ to describe a spoiled identity that discredits a person in society. The author quoted stigma as a “deeply discrediting attribute” that reduces the bearer “from a whole and usual person to a tainted, discounted one” (Goffman, 1963). As Corrigan and Watson (2002) state, stigma constitutes of three fundamental psychological components: stereotype, prejudice and discrimination. Stereotype entails a negative belief about the self or a group. Consequently, a prejudiced individual agrees with this negative belief, thereby triggering an emotional reaction. Finally, prejudice leads to the behavioural response termed discrimination.

Stigma is a multifaceted term and a variety of subtypes has been described in literature. Public stigma entails the reaction and attitude that the general public has towards people dealing with a mental illness. This type of stigma is further subclassified in personal stigma (one’s own views of a stigmatized group) and perceived stigma (one’s own perception about the extent to which people have a stigmatizing reaction towards a stigmatized group) (Clement et al., 2015; Kosyluk et al., 2016). A stigmatized individual may experience internalized or self-stigma, by which the affected holds stigmatizing views about oneself and thus deems oneself as socially unacceptable. A fourth type of stigma constitutes attitudes towards help-seeking that includes “the perception of a need for help, stigma tolerance associated with seeking such services, openness regarding one’s problem and confidence that the help will be of assistance” (Schnyder et al., 2017).

A model developed by Vogel *et al.* (2007) insinuates that public stigma, self-stigma and negative attitudes towards help-seeking consequently reduce willingness to seek psychological treatment. Previous studies have indicated that those with a higher level of mental health literacy are less likely to hold stigmatizing attitudes against mental health (Jung et al., 2017; Milin et al., 2016). However, unclarity exists whether the relationship between mental health literacy and stigma is causal. As Holman states (2015), mental health-related stigma can distort knowledge and understanding around mental health, suggesting an interplay between mental health literacy and stigma. Meanwhile, Kim (2021) proposes that “mental health stigma serves as an intervening role between mental health literacy and help-seeking attitudes” (p. 4). Given together, Figure 1 presents a model by which mental health literacy and stigma cooperate to influence the attitudes towards help-seeking and therefore willingness to seek professional treatment for mental health concerns.

Fig. 1: Proposed model depicting the correlation between mental health literacy, mental health stigma and willingness to seek help.

The critical role of newspapers in framing mental health-related stigma

It is widely argued that mass media has the ability to either portray mental illness in a favourable light or worsen and maintain mental health-related stigmatization among its audiences (Gaebel et al., 2017). The media presents an important vehicle for conveying daily knowledge, sense-making and opinions about contemporary society to the general public (Burns et al., 2022). As such, mass media are “channels of communication intended to reach large numbers, which are not dependent on person-to-person contact” (Friedman, 2020). Even in the digital age, mass media in the form of newspapers is regarded as a primary source for obtaining knowledge about mental illness among the general public. Hence, newspapers may hold the power to influence the perception of mental health among its readers.

The stigmatizing or destigmatizing stance of the newspaper media depends on how the information is ‘framed’. Framing refers to how news regarding a topic is constructed, organized, presented, and interpreted in the media (Sieff, 2003). As Altheide and Schneider (2013) state, “frames focus on what will be discussed, how it will be discussed, and, above all, how it will *not* be discussed” (p. 61). As such, journalists can present mental health correctly or misleading, thereby influencing levels of mental health literacy, stigmatization and willingness to seek professional help among the readers of newspapers.

Alarmingly, two studies conducted in Australia and Canada revealed that upcoming journalists hold stigmatizing attitudes towards people with mental health conditions (Burns et al., 2022; Stuart et al., 2011). They tend to prefer to social distance from an individual who has a mental illness diagnosis, while 50% also agrees with the stereotype that people with a mental illness can be unpredictable and dangerous. Concerningly, even when confronted with information of how media shapes the biased portrait of mental health illnesses, more than half of upcoming journalists did not state to be more aware of their wording and phrasing when writing future stories about mental health (Stuart et al., 2011).

The stigmatizing views of journalists are likely, may it be unconsciously, reflected in the reporting of mental illnesses in newspaper media. Consistently over decades, newspaper media coverage of mental illnesses have been framed in an overwhelmingly negative manner. A plethora of studies have found a common portrayal of the mentally ill having dangerous and violent attributes (Klin & Lemish, 2008). This goes as far back to the 1950s, in which psychotic people were pinpointed as ‘dirty and dangerous’ in the media (Taylor, 1957, p. 201). Individuals with mental health conditions are oftentimes, up to 30% of the cases, portrayed as perpetrators or suspects of a crime. In reality however, these individuals are fourteen times more likely to be victims of a crime (Arneaud et al., 2022; Chen & Lawrie, 2017).

Additionally, mental health-related news articles have the tendency to be framed in an sensationalist fashion with dramatic headlines on the front page, as to sell the news by grabbing the readers’ attention (Angermeyer & Schulze, 2001; Murphy et al., 2013). As an example, various newspapers in the USA in the late 1990s included the headlines *Subway psycho’s deadly shove* and *Get the violent crazies off our streets* (Friedman, 2020, p. 57). As of more recently, multiple studies have still recognized biased newspaper articles regarding mental health disorders, thereby perpetuating stigmatization in our society (Gallagher et al., 2023; Li et al., 2021; Miller et al., 2020; Whitley et al., 2015; Zolezzi et al.,

2020). With a speculative rising number of news reporting on mental health as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, this issue becomes ever more pressing (Arneaud et al., 2022).

The potential of newspapers to destigmatize mental health

On the opposite side of the coin, printed media that positively frames mental health may destigmatize this topic. By correctly informing about a mental health-related topic, newspapers may hold the power to improve levels of mental health literacy and thereby to attenuate stigmatizing attitudes towards mental health. Describing biological or genetic origins of a mental disorder in news articles potentially hampers blame towards the individual experiencing a mental health condition (Slopen et al., 2007). Indeed, Phelan (2002) stated that the genetic revolution brings forward the perception of mental illnesses as genetically based rather than attributed to a weak character. Opposingly, implementing solely biological causes of a mental disorder in news articles can convey the notion that a mental illness is hard-wired, leading the general public to misleadingly believe a mental illness is a permanent disease. Hence, stating both environmental factors and themes of recovery attributes to the perception that mental illnesses can be temporarily caused and overcome over a lifetime (Corrigan et al., 2005; Elliott et al., 2012).

Presumably, the source that triggers journalists to write mental health-related news articles can also influence the level of stigma that news articles bring forward. News triggers include a case study, involvement of high profile people, tragedy and novel research (Holland, 2018). When journalists apply a case study as their main source, people who have experienced a mental illness are placed on the foreground. Applying this ‘human interest frame’ can destigmatize mental disorders: after all, those having this condition are portrayed positively and sympathetically in this manner (Rhydderch et al., 2016). Meanwhile, the absence of voices of individuals with mental illnesses in newspapers “reinforces the public suspicions that those with mental illnesses are unable—too disordered, too disorganized, too unreliable—to speak for themselves” (Wahl, 2003). Additionally, quoting high profile and public figure oftentimes positively influences the perception of mental health as it enables readers to relate to mental health conditions (Holland, 2018).

Intriguingly, scientific news triggers including new research and ‘breakthroughs’ are scarce in mental health-related news articles in comparison with articles covering news regarding physical health and illness. As one journalist states: “I think there’s a general kind of belief that mental health problems happen to other people, but [...] cancer or whatever, that could happen to me” (Holland, 2018, p. 8). Hence, journalists may refrain from writing articles about new research around mental health as they perceive readers do not care much about the topic. However arguably, news articles covering scientific and novel research in the field of mental health could provide readers with objective and thereby non-stigmatizing information.

Furthermore, consulting experts in the field of mental health and incorporating quotes and paraphrases could reflect objectivity in mental health-related news articles. To illustrate, a study performed by Nairn (1999) uncovered that involving psychiatrists as opposed to lay persons as source of information for news articles results in a less negative presentation of mental health. Taken together, journalists are able to apply stigmatizing elements – crime – and destigmatizing elements – causes, news triggers and quotations – in their writings about mental health, which dictates the stance of newspapers towards mental health.

Interactions with mental illness and newspaper type

Notably, previous studies have pinpointed two prominent confounding factors influencing how mental health is portrayed in printed media: the type of mental illness presented and the type of newspaper the article is published in. Newspapers discuss depression more often than anxiety disorders, despite the high prevalence of anxiety disorders in the global population (Arneaud et al., 2022; Kenez et al., 2015; Zolezzi et al., 2020). Indeed, anxiety disorders tend to be overlooked by research (Kenez et al., 2015). This disproportionate attention also holds true for schizophrenia, as it has been covered disproportionately well in news articles elsewhere of up to 23% in oftentimes sensationalist articles illustrating violence and crime (Arneaud et al., 2022; Gallagher et al., 2023). In reality however, 0.3% of the global population lives with this disorder as of 2022 (World Health Organization, 2022).

As for type of newspaper, a large body of studies elsewhere have highlighted that tabloid newspapers are more likely to portray a stigmatizing stance towards mental health in comparison to broadsheet newspapers (Gallagher et al., 2023; Li et al., 2021; Whitley & Wang, 2017). Particularly embedded in the British media culture, tabloids are regarded as popular newspapers focusing on sports, scandal and popular entertainment (Johansson, 2007). Hereby, tabloid journalists aim to sell news by using a judgmental or sensationalist tone, accompanied with shocking headlines and imagery to strengthen the emotional impact among readers (Hanusch, 2013). Altogether, journalists apply either stigmatizing or destigmatizing elements around mental health considering the type of mental illness that is covered and the type of newspapers the article is published in.

The portrayal of mental health in Dutch newspapers

A growing body of content analyses has shed light on applied frames on mental health topics in newspapers in countries including Canada (Whitley et al., 2015), Australia (Kenez et al., 2015), India (Subramanian, 2019), Qatar (Zolezzi et al., 2020), Uganda (Miller et al., 2020), South Africa (Masinga et al., 2022), the United Kingdom (Li et al., 2021; Murphy et al., 2013) and Ireland (Gallagher et al., 2023). Rather curiously, no content analysis has been conducted on Dutch mental health-related news articles to the best of our knowledge. Mental health is however a concerning subject within the Netherlands: 18.9% of the Dutch population has been diagnosed with a mental disorder as of 2022 (Trimbos Instituut, 2023). In line with the global pattern, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has struck the mental health of Dutch citizens: those without previous symptoms of mental health conditions experienced an increase in depressive and anxiety symptoms during the pandemic (Pan et al., 2021).

Understanding about how Dutch newspapers cover mental health-related news elucidates what information the Dutch general public receives about mental health and whether the information may contain stigmatizing or destigmatizing elements. Because people in the Netherlands predominantly receive information around mental illnesses by newspaper media, we also deem it necessary to explore whether different types of mental illnesses are proportionally discussed in Dutch news articles. Furthermore, the frequency of different sources that journalists employ for writing mental health-related news and its consequent influence on stigmatization remains largely unexplored terrain. A scarce body of research has noted a lack of news articles focusing on human interest stories and novel research around mental health in Australia and New Zealand (Holland, 2018; R. G. Nairn & Coverdale, 2005). However, to the best of our knowledge, it has yet to be studied in both the Netherlands as well as the post COVID-19 newspaper landscape.

Lastly, the Dutch newspaper landscape has a less clear distinction with regards to tabloid vs. broadsheet newspapers in comparison to the UK (Legius, 2015). Notably, of all the highly-distributed Dutch national newspapers, *De Telegraaf* arguably best resembles a tabloid newspaper, thereby highlighting sensational stories and elaborating on sports and showbiz. As such, *De Telegraaf* describes itself as a newspaper for the common man. Meanwhile, *De Volkskrant* situates itself on the other side of the spectrum, presenting itself as a quality newspaper and taking a more intellectual approach in portraying its news (Roelofs, 2022). Given previous results suggesting a particular stigmatizing stance on mental health among tabloids in comparison to broadsheet newspapers, it would be beneficial to investigate whether distinct types of newspapers that are distributed throughout the Netherlands portray mental health in a different manner as well (Gallagher et al., 2023; Li et al., 2021; Whitley & Wang, 2017).

Research objectives

In light of the current knowledge gaps, this study seeks to explore the frames that Dutch newspapers utilize when covering news about mental health. Hence, our objectives are to examine the following exploratory research questions:

RQ1: How are different types of mental illnesses incorporated and portrayed in Dutch newspaper articles?

RQ2: How and in what degree do Dutch news articles around mental health use stigmatizing or anti-stigmatizing elements?

RQ3: Do different Dutch newspapers portray the topic of mental health differently?

RQ4: How do different types of news sources influence the stigmatizing or anti-stigmatizing nature of Dutch news articles?

In line with previous findings we anticipate more stigmatization and negative framing of mental health problems in Dutch newspapers relative to destigmatized framing. Here, we also expect that schizophrenia is particularly linked with violence and crime, as perceived in previous research (Gallagher et al., 2023; Kenez et al., 2015). We expect that mood disorders including depression will be the most covered mental illness in Dutch newspapers, based upon previous literature (Arneaud et al., 2022; Kenez et al., 2015; Zolezzi et al., 2020). Furthermore, it is to be expected that schizophrenia is covered disproportionately well in Dutch newspapers (R. G. Nairn & Coverdale, 2005). Finally, we expect that among Dutch national newspapers, *De Telegraaf* constitutes the most stigmatizing stance with regards to portraying mental health.

Method

Data selection

Newspaper articles were sourced from five national Dutch newspapers distributed throughout the Netherlands: *De Telegraaf*, *Algemeen Dagblad*, *De Volkskrant*, *NRC* and *Trouw*. These newspapers were selected as they belong to the highest distributed national newspapers in the Netherlands and capture a homogenous group of reader profiles in terms of gender and age (Table 1) (Grimm, 2022a, 2022b). News articles published in the selected printed Dutch newspapers were retrieved from the *Nexis Uni* online database available for universities. This database falls under the umbrella of the *Lexis Nexis* database, which has been successfully used in previous research regarding mental health framing (Li et al., 2021).

Table 1: Outline of selected Dutch national newspapers

Newspaper	Circulation (printed)	Ownership group	Gender		Age		
			Male	Female	13-34	35-49	50+
De Telegraaf	752,000 (Monday to Friday) 1,049,000 (Saturday)	Mediahuis Nederland	50%	50%	27%	24%	49%
Algemeen Dagblad	838,000 (Monday to Friday) 1,098,000 (Saturday)	DPG Media	51%	49%	30%	25%	45%
De Volkskrant	459,000 (Monday to Friday) 794,000 (Saturday)	DPG Media	50%	50%	32%	21%	47%
NRC	268,000 (Monday to Friday) 535,000 (Saturday)	Mediahuis	51%	49%	31%	26%	44%
Trouw	213,000 (Monday to Friday) 336,000 (Saturday)	DPG Media	52%	48%	29%	22%	49%

Data retrieved from NMO Print & Merken Monitor 2022-II (Grimm, 2022a) and NMO Print & Merken Monitor 2021 IV (Grimm, 2022b)

Newspaper articles were collected during the search period of 10th of October till 19th of December 2022 (10 weeks). The rationale behind the chosen time period was based on multiple arguments: firstly, we solely aimed to include newspaper articles published post COVID-19 pandemic after which COVID-19 measures have been lifted in the Netherlands (June 2022). Secondly, we omit the summer high season during which both newspaper readers and journalists are on holidays. Later time periods were not chosen due to Blue Monday in January 2023 and the Dutch provincial elections in March 2023, as it could potentially bias the amount of published news articles about mental health.

Search terms

Consulting existing literature and reports, we devised an initial list of Dutch terms related to mental health to collect only relevant news articles (Supplementary Table S1). Dutch translations of terms were drawn from previous research by Kenez et al. (2015) and Li et al. (2021), who examined mental health framing in Australian and British newspapers, respectively. To allow for specificity, we incorporated terms related to several types of mental illnesses, including depressive, bipolar, anxiety, obsessive compulsive and schizophrenic disorders. Initially, the full texts of articles were screened using the following terms (* = wildcard): 'mentaal OR mentale gezondheid OR mentaal welbevinden OR mentale ziekte* OR mentale klacht* OR mentale aandoening* OR psychisch* OR psychologisch OR geestelijk* OR therapie OR therapeut* OR psycho* OR psychiatrisch* OR psychiater OR psychiatrische instelling

OR psychiatrische inrichting OR kliniek or stoornis* OR depressie* OR bipolair* OR manie OR manisch OR somber OR lusteloos OR burn-out OR angst* OR paniek OR paniekaanval OR dwangstoornis* OR dwangneurose* OR schizo*. Here, a wildcard is applied to search for alternative spellings or variations of a word (e.g. depression* includes depressions). After the pilot screening, we added additional general search terms related to mental health: burn-outklacht* or eetstoornis* or angststoornis*. In total, the complete search term list consisted of 38 terms.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Figure 2 presents the roadmap followed for the article screening process. The initial screening on the *Lexis Nexis Uni* database using our list of search terms yielded 3345 Dutch newspaper articles, after which duplicate articles were manually discarded. No threshold for word count was set. Articles were excluded if they were published in the newspaper sections of Sports, obituaries and Letters to the Editor. Likewise, opinionated articles, columns, film, theatre and book reviews, horoscopes, puzzles, food recipes and weather forecasts were omitted. Articles discussing neurodevelopmental and substance use disorders were excluded. Articles were removed from the dataset if the search term was discussed in a context unrelated to mental health. As examples, articles mentioning the economic term ‘great depression’ (Dutch: *grote depressie*) and ‘the Dutch language proficiency among youth is dispiriting’ (Dutch: *Nederlands taalniveau onder jongeren stemt somber*) were removed.

News articles were deemed eligible if the main focus was on mental health, either discussed in a general sense or by covering one or more symptoms. Articles were also included if the focus was on a mental health-related topic, for instance a medical intervention or a crime involving an individual coping with a mental health condition. For the latter example, the article would only be included if the crime was explicitly linked to an individual with a mental health condition; a sole mention of a tbs-sentence or tbs-clinic would not suffice. Mental health or a mental health-related topic were regarded as a main focus if the topic was mentioned in either the lead or one of the first two paragraphs of the article.

Occasionally, mental health or a mental health-related topic was not the main focus of the article. In order to be included, the article was required to discuss two or more of the following inclusion criteria: causes, symptoms or definitions of a mental health condition; medical intervention, self-treatment, recovery or crime. A selection of these articles were found to mention one or more of the criteria rather than discussing it. Hereby, it was decided to introduce a quantitative threshold: the articles were only eligible if it contained four different search terms (approximately 10% of the search term list) in the text. Among the initial list of articles, 120 were deemed eligible (see Figure 2).

Coding of articles

Previous literature conducting similar research was consulted in creating an initial codebook containing qualitative and quantitative variables (Li et al., 2021; Whitley et al., 2015). Here, an individual news article was regarded as the unit of analysis. The coding was guided by establishing five categories: (1) descriptive variables of the article (2) mental illness classification (3) news triggers (4) stigmatization of mental health condition (5) destigmatization of mental health condition. The following descriptive variables of the article were collected: newspaper origin; day of publication; year of publication; and name of publication. The types of news triggers were distinguished as either scientific or non-scientific. Research by Kristensen et al (2021), in which news triggers for news articles around physics were studied, was consulted in creating this section of the codebook. Mental illnesses were classified by their official name according to DSM-5 (American Psychiatric Association & American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Although burn-out is not classified as a mental illness by DSM-5, it has been

considered a mental disorder as of 2019 by ICD-11 (World Health Organization, 2019a). Also given the quickly gained global significance of the disease, we classified burn-out as a mental illness in our study (Schaufeli et al., 2009).

Fig. 2: Process of article screening. Flowchart is adapted from PRISM 2020 (Page et al., 2021)

Aside from the stigmatizing link between mental health and crime that has been found in newspapers elsewhere, substance abuse has also been regarded as a component of stigmatization of mental illnesses (Adlaf et al., 2009). It further feeds the image that it is the individual's own fault to develop a mental disorder. Hence, drawn upon previous literature, mental health-related stigmatization in news articles was coded by the following separate elements: the prevalence of a mental health condition connected to a crime or substance abuse and the portrayal of a mental disorder as an individual's own fault. Meanwhile, destigmatization of mental health was measured by the prevalence of a biological and/or environmental cause of a mental health condition; quotation of an expert in the field of mental health, individual experiencing a mental health condition and/or celebrity; partial or successful

recovery of an individual with a mental disorder and formal and/or informal mental health intervention.

With an initial version of the codebook, the author (BS) coded several mental health-related articles to explore whether the codebook was complete during a two-week pilot study. After refining several questions, 21% (n=25) articles of the article sample were randomly selected, after which the first author (BS) and a second coder (LX) coded quantitative data independently. For all qualitative codes, the author (BS) performed inductive thematic analysis independently after coding all articles: from a ground-up approach, codes were read and distinguished in small groups. From here, major categories emerged. To illustrate, different types of medicines mentioned in terms of mental health interventions were grouped together, establishing multiple groups among which *antidepressants* and *antipsychotics*. Together, these groups were labelled the overarching category of *medication*. The established categories were sent to a second coder (DR), who independently labelled qualitative codes from a random selection of articles under a category.

Interrater reliability, entailing the degree of consistent coding between the individuals, was tested by Krippendorff's α coefficient and percentage agreement (Krippendorff, 1970). For our quantitative data, we encountered a classical paradox by which the coefficient returns low values while the level of agreement is high among coders, as Krippendorff's α is sensitive to an uneven distribution of scores. As an example, a variable returned a Krippendorff's α of 0.466 while percentage agreement was 91.7%. Therefore, substantial agreement between coders was confirmed when the tests yielded both a percentage agreement higher than 80% and a Krippendorff's α value of 0.75. If this threshold was not met for a variable, the variable was rephrased until agreement was confirmed.

Notably, Krippendorff's α and percentage agreement were found to be low for a substantial amount of qualitative variables. As such, themes that were established to measure the types of environmental causes mentioned in articles were initially deemed too subjective (Krippendorff's $\alpha=0.049$). Therefore, we opted for a "negotiated agreement" approach by which the first and second coder discussed disagreements in an effort to resolve discrepancies (Campbell et al., 2013). By applying this negotiated agreement method, percentage agreement for the variable measuring crime and substance abuse raised to 78%. As for the low Krippendorff's α of 0.049 for the variable measuring environmental causes, it was found that the theme of environmental factors was interpreted differently between coders. By adding a definition to the theme, the coders reconciled and a 100% agreement rate was met. It was further found that the low score of Krippendorff's $\alpha = -0.0345$ for the variable measuring mental health intervention was largely established due to empty responses and wrongly reading by one coder per accident. Secondly, one coder took into account the context of a mental health intervention (example: "*I was not ready for therapy*"), while the variable measured only the prevalence of a mentioned mental health condition, irrespective of the context. After discussion, a negotiated agreement percentage of 75% was reached. In contrast, the variable measuring *self-help behaviour tips* was not met with agreement. Hence, the corresponding data was removed for data analysis.

An overview of the quantitative and qualitative variables and accompanying Krippendorff's α and percentage agreement is listed in Supplementary Table S2 and S3, respectively. The complete codebook, constituting 51 variables, can be found in Supplementary Materials B.

Data analysis

All data was collected in an Excel spreadsheet and consequently entered into RStudio Version 1.4.1717 (RStudio Team, 2020). Frequencies (% , N) of published articles, mentioned mental illnesses, news

triggers and elements of stigmatization and destigmatization were calculated. Chi-square tests of independence (χ^2) were performed to determine whether frequencies of the aforementioned variables were different among each other (McHugh, 2013). If more than 20% of the expected counts were below five or if an individual expected count was lower than one, a Fisher's Exact test was used (Yates et al., 1999).

To investigate both the correlation between mentioned types of mental illnesses and (de)stigmatizing elements and the correlation between types of newspapers and (de)stigmatizing elements, we initially opted to perform a multinomial logistic regression. However, it was decided that this analysis was beyond the scope of this research due to time constraints and its unsuitability to distinctively answer our primary research objectives. Hence, Chi-square tests of independence (χ^2) were performed to uncover the correlation. Graphical visualisations were made with GraphPad Prism version 9.5.1. for Windows, GraphPad Software, Boston, Massachusetts, USA. For all statistical tests, a threshold of $\alpha < 0.05$ was set.

Results

Descriptives of collected article sample

In total, 120 articles from five Dutch newspapers were collected, published between October and December during a 10-week period. The majority of included articles were published in *De Telegraaf* (n=32, 27%), followed by *Algemeen Dagblad* with 26 articles (22%), *Trouw* with 22 articles (18%), *De Volkskrant* with 21 articles (18%) and *NRC* with 19 articles (16%). As shown in Table 2, the majority of the articles was published on Saturdays (34%) – the day in which newspapers have the highest circulation and come with supplements in the Netherlands (Grimm, 2020). Articles published in *De Volkskrant* had the highest mean word count of 1712, while the identified articles in *De Telegraaf* had the lowest by 528. Mental health or a mental health-related topic was the main focus in 83% of the article sample (n=100). Only 18% (n=21) of all articles linked mental health, either negatively or positively, with COVID-19 (Supplementary Table S4).

Table 2: Distribution of article publication per day of the week in Dutch newspapers

Newspaper	Day of the week (N)						Total
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	
De Telegraaf	7	6	7	4	3	5	32
Algemeen Dagblad	2	1	7	2	5	9	26
De Volkskrant	1	1	5	2	2	10	21
NRC	6	1	1	1	3	7	19
Trouw	2	1	2	3	4	10	22
Total	18	10	22	12	17	41	120

Incorporation of mental illnesses in Dutch newspapers

Mental illness classification

As presented in RQ1, we first sought to identify which mental health illnesses are covered in the Dutch newspaper landscape. Of the 120 articles identified, 64% (n=77) mentioned at least one mental illness by its official name. Seventeen types of mental illnesses were covered in our article sample. Depression was the most prominent type of mental illness mentioned: the term was prevalent in 35% (n=42) of the articles. This was followed by burn-out (20%, n=24), anxiety disorder (17%, n=20), (chronic) posttraumatic stress disorder ((C)PTSD) (9%, n=11), and personality disorder (3%, n=4) (Figure 2A). Seven types of mental disorders accounted for less than 1% of the articles. The complete outline of classification and prevalence of mental disorders can be found in Supplementary Table S5.

Continuing our analysis with the five most prevalent mental illnesses in our article collection, we next investigated whether types of mental illnesses were mentioned in combination with others in our news articles. Depression was mentioned simultaneously with anxiety disorder 29%; combined with both anxiety disorder and burnout 10% and mentioned together with (C)PTSD 7% of the times. Of the 24 times burn-out was coined in our articles, it was most often incorporated solely in our articles (17 times, 71%). Interestingly, anxiety disorder was never solely mentioned. A visual representation of the prevalence of combined mental illnesses can be found in Supplementary Figure S1.

Prevalence of symptoms addressed per mental illness

As providing knowledge about mental health improves mental health literacy and arguably reduces mental health-related stigma, we next explored the prevalence of descriptions of mental illnesses in the Dutch newspaper landscape. Of the article sample, 29% (n=35) gave at least one description/symptom of a mental illness (Figure 2B). For depression, symptoms were given 26% of the times this disease was mentioned (n=12). This percentage was higher for both burn-out and (C)PTSD by 50% and 55%, respectively. Interestingly, articles only rarely contained symptoms for anxiety disorder (10%, n=2). Dutch newspapers failed to give descriptions for personality disorder in our article sample. A complete overview of the prevalence of symptoms given per mental illness is found in Supplementary Table S6.

To investigate whether Dutch newspapers provide accurate knowledge regarding mental illnesses, deductive coding was employed to analyze the symptoms mentioned for the five most prevalent mental illnesses covered in our article sample. Mentioned symptoms were categorized into criteria that DSM-5 applies to diagnose these mental illnesses. For burn-out, symptoms were categorized in criteria according to ICD-11. If a description or symptom in our data did not fit a particular criterium, a new category was established. As illustrated in Figure 2C, symptoms given for depression in our article sample could be categorized in nine categories. Most often, depression was characterized by feeling depressed (Dutch: somber), followed by experiencing tiredness, fatigue, or low energy, or decreased efficiency with which routine tasks are completed. Although anxious thoughts or panic attacks are not regarded as criteria for depression in the DSM-5, these descriptions were occasionally used for depression in our articles. Additionally, one article described depression as the feeling of being trapped inside one's own body, while this is not perceived as a criterium for depression in the DSM-5.

Symptoms of burn-out could be distinguished into seven categories, of which three represent the dimensions of which burn-out is described by ICD-11 (Figure 2D). Of these dimensions, the majority of given symptoms were in line with feeling energy depleted or exhausted (n=10). On the contrary, symptoms were rarely given for the dimensions of reduced professional efficacy and increased mental distance from one's job or feelings of negativism or cynicism related to one's job (n=1). Meanwhile, burn-out has been described as having a depressed or anxious mood in our articles, corresponding to criteria of depression and anxiety disorder, respectively.

Descriptions of anxiety disorder could only be categorized in two criteria (Figure 2E). Here, anxiety disorder was mostly described by experiencing physical symptoms including sweating and heavy breathing, which is not regarded as a criterium of the disease in the DSM-5. In contrast, symptoms were elaborately given to (C)PTSD, categorized in nine criteria given by DSM-5 (Figure 2F). Here, this mental illness was most often characterized by having recurrent distressing dreams regarding the traumatic event(s) and experiencing a persistent negative emotional state such as fear and anxiety (both n=3).

Stigmatizing elements in Dutch printed media

Crime, substance abuse and mental health

To study whether and to what degree Dutch newspapers incorporate stigmatizing elements surrounding the topic of mental health, we explored how often articles connected mental health with crime. Data revealed that 25% (n=30) of all articles referenced both mental health and crime. The majority of these articles referenced an individual with a mental health condition as the perpetrator of a crime (18%, n=21). In 5% (n=6) of our sample, the individual with a mental health condition was

Fig. 2: Incorporation of mental illnesses in national Dutch newspapers. (A) Prevalence of mental illnesses mentioned in five national Dutch newspapers, calculated by the count of a mentioned mental illness divided by the total amount of articles collected in *De Telegraaf* (n=32), *Algemeen Dagblad* (n=26), *De Volkskrant* (n=21), *NRC* (n=19) and *Trouw* (n=22). The percentage number depicted above the mental illness represents its prevalence in the whole article sample (n=120). (B) Prevalence of a definition, description or symptom given for a mental illness. This was calculated by the count of definition, description or symptom given divided by the amount of times a mental illness is mentioned per Dutch newspaper. (C) Count of categorized definitions, descriptions or symptoms given for depression (D) burn-out (E) anxiety disorder and (F) posttraumatic stress

disorder. (C)PTSD, (Chronic) Posttraumatic Stress Disorder. * illustrates symptoms that do not corresponds with those in the DSM-5 or ICD-11 (burn-out).

depicted as a suspect for committing a crime. Three percent (n=3) of the collected articles concerned an individual with a mental health condition as a victim of a crime. Eleven percent of our articles (n=13) referenced mental health with substance abuse. Four percent of our articles (n=5) indicated that mental health conditions are a consequence of the lack of an individual's resilience. A complete overview of the prevalence of stigmatizing elements in Dutch newspapers is outlined in Table 3.

Performing a thematic analysis, the mentioned crimes in our article sample were distinguished in nine categories. Here, homicide was the most prevalent crime discussed for perpetrators and suspects by 14% (n=17) and 5% (n=6), respectively. As for victims with a mental illness, sexual assault was the only crime mentioned (3%, n=3). Types of substance abuse were categorized into three categories, including alcohol, drug usage and medicine misuse. Here, drug abuse was often mentioned in 7% (n=8) of all collected articles. Results from the thematic analysis are outlined in Supplementary Table S7.

Table 3: Stigmatizing elements incorporated in Dutch national newspapers

Stigmatizing elements	De Telegraaf N (%)	AD N (%)	De Volkskrant N (%)	NRC N (%)	Trouw N (%)	Total N (%)
Crime	12 (10)	9 (8)	3 (3)	3 (3)	3 (3)	30 (25)
Perpetrator	8 (7)	7 (6)	1 (<1)	3 (3)	2 (2)	21 (18)
Suspect	4 (3)	2 (2)	-	-	-	6 (5)
Victim	-	-	2 (2)	-	1 (<1)	3 (3)
Substance abuse	3 (3)	3 (3)	1 (<1)	2 (2)	4 (3)	13 (11)
Lack of resilience	3 (3)	2 (2)	-	-	-	5 (4)

-; indicates 0 (0)

Correlation between type of mental illness and destigmatizing elements

To investigate whether the type of mental illness influences the degree of which an article contains stigmatizing elements, we explored the connection of our five most-mentioned mental illnesses to a crime, substance abuse or proposed lack of an individual's resilience. Although not included in the top five, schizophrenia was included to our analysis, as this mental illness was previously found to be particularly linked with stigmatizing elements in newspapers elsewhere.

As shown in Figure 3A, the mental illness of personality disorder and schizophrenia tended to be more likely to be connected with crime in articles compared to others. However, while the Fisher's exact test indicated a significant correlation between types of mental illness and the prevalence of crime ($p=0.014$), post-hoc pairwise testing with FDR adjusted p-value revealed no significant correlation, presumably due to the small sample size. We did not find a significant correlation between types of mental illnesses with substance abuse and lack of individual's resilience (Supplementary Figure S2A).

Correlation between type of newspaper and destigmatizing elements

We next explored whether the type of newspaper influences the prevalence of stigmatizing elements around mental health in articles. Although Supplementary Figure S3A shows a higher likeliness for *De Telegraaf* and *Algemeen Dagblad* to publish mental health-related articles connected to crime

compared to others, a Fisher's exact test revealed no significant correlation between types of newspapers and mentioned mental-health related crime in news articles ($p=0.12$). Similarly, no correlations were found between types of newspapers and frequency of mentioned mental health-related substance abuse. Also, we found no correlation between type of newspaper and lack of an individual's resilience ($p=0.29$) (Supplementary Figure S3A).

Stigmatizing elements in Dutch printed media

Biological and environmental causes of mental illnesses

We next sought to investigate the presence of destigmatizing elements around mental health in Dutch news articles, including the implementation of causes of mental illnesses. A complete overview of the prevalence of stigmatizing elements in Dutch newspapers is outlined in Supplementary Table S8. It was found that 53% of the article sample included a cause of a mental health condition. Herein, an environmental cause was mentioned in 50% of the articles ($n=60$). Biological causes were described in 13% of the articles ($n=16$). A genetic disposition was most often mentioned as a biological cause for a mental health condition (10%, $n=12$).

Environmental causes were categorized into nine groups, of which the causes were most frequently categorized as stress or trauma/traumatic experiences (26%, $n=31$). An example includes: "*We moved to Hoorn, I had to go to a new high school, it were big changes that confused me deeply*". Sixteen percent of the articles ($n=19$) noted socio-economic factors: "*Inequality has risen, the pressure to perform on school is becoming higher and people are given more responsibility over the years*". Characteristic traits of the individual were mentioned in 12% of the articles ($n=14$) including perfectionism. Supplementary Table S9 lists complete overview of mentioned biological and environmental causes and corresponding prevalence.

Considering types of mental illnesses, we found a pattern by which articles discussing personality disorder and schizophrenia were less likely to include biological or environmental causes, Fisher's exact test, $p=0.04$ (Figure 3B). However, post-hoc comparisons yielded no significance. Pearson's Chi-squared test for independence demonstrated a significant correlation between types of newspapers and frequency of mentioned biological or environmental causes, $\chi^2(4, N=120)=22.275$, $p=0.0002$ (Figure 4A). Post-hoc pairwise tested revealed a significant difference in frequency of mentioned causes between *De Telegraaf* vs. *Volkskrant* (adjusted $p=0.01$), *NRC* (adjusted $p=0.006$), and *Trouw* (adjusted $p=0.01$). Additionally, differences between *AD* and *NRC* were found ($p=0.04$).

Quotes by experts in mental health and others

Considering quotations, mental health experts were most frequently quoted; almost half of all articles (48%, $n=57$) incorporated a quote from a mental health expert. Likewise, a large portion of articles included a quote from either an individual experiencing a mental illness or relative (44%, $n=53$). A celebrity was quoted in 17% of all articles ($n=20$).

A Fisher's exact test showed a significant correlation between the frequency of quotes from experts and types of mental illnesses ($p=0.02$). Hereof, Figure 3B indicates that burn-out was least likely to be associated with a quoted mental health expert, while schizophrenia was most likely. While post-hoc pairwise testing indeed showed a significant correlation of burn-out vs. depression ($p=0.005$), anxiety disorder ($p=0.01$) and schizophrenia ($p=0.04$), an FDR adjusted p-value revealed no significant result. No significant correlations were found between mental illness and frequency of quotes from individuals experiencing mental health conditions or relatives and celebrities (Supplementary Figure S2B).

Although our data indicated a trend in which *De Telegraaf* and *Algemeen Dagblad* were less likely to incorporate a quote from a mental health expert in their articles compared to others, no significant result was harboured ($\chi^2(4, N=120)=8.447, p=0.08$) (Figure 4). Types of newspapers were not correlated with the quotations from individuals experiencing a mental health condition or relatives, and from celebrities (Supplementary Figure S3B).

Recovery and mental health interventions

In total, 22% of the article sample (n=26) mentioned successful or partial recovery of a mental illness. A type of mental health intervention was covered in 42% of the article sample (n=50). Inductive coding revealed that medicines are the predominant mental health intervention mentioned, in 19% of all articles (n=23). Unspecified therapies were mentioned in 13% of all articles (n=15). Therapies including EMDR (5%, n= 6), psychotherapy (5%, n= 6) and cognitive-behavioural therapy (3%, n=4) were among the most-mentioned specified therapies. Self-help behavioural tips for maintaining good mental health were mentioned in 17% of all articles (n=20). A full outline of mentioned mental health interventions and corresponding prevalence is given in Supplementary Table S10.

Notably, a strong significant association was found between type of mental illness and mentioned mental health interventions (Fisher's exact test, $p=0.0002$). Post-hoc pairwise testing revealed that the frequency of mentioned mental health interventions differs significantly between depression and burn-out (*adjusted* $p=0.03$). Additionally, significant differences between PTSD vs. depression (*adjusted* $p=0.02$), vs. burn-out (*adjusted* $p=0.0002$), vs. anxiety disorder (*adjusted* $p=0.02$) and vs. personality disorder (*adjusted* $p=0.02$) were found. Figure 3B indeed illustrates that articles mentioning PTSD were most likely to incorporate a mental health intervention. No significant association between type of mental illness and partial or successful recovery was discovered. Also, we found no significant correlation between type of mental illness and self-help behaviour tips (Supplementary Figure S2B).

We perceived a trend in which *De Telegraaf* and *Algemeen Dagblad* were less likely than others to include mental health interventions in their articles (Figure 4). However, no significance was reached ($\chi^2(4, N=120)=8.4861, p=0.08$). Furthermore, we found no significant correlation between types of newspaper and mentioned recovery, and between types of newspaper and self-help behaviour tips.

Type of news source and (de)stigmatization of mental health

Our final objective was to investigate whether there is a correlation between the type of news trigger used for writing a news article and the frequency of mentioned (de)stigmatizing elements around mental health. It was found that predominantly non-scientific sources triggered the writing of mental health-related articles within our sample (78%, n=93). Hereof, a crime was the most common news trigger in 20% of the articles (n=24), followed by a (public) health concern with no scientific report or study attached (15%, n=18). Scientific sources triggered the writing of 23% of the articles (n=27) in our article selection, of which the most common scientific source entailed a new research article, report, scientific book or medical intervention that is published or discussed (20%, n=24). Supplementary Table S11 gives a complete outline of prevalence of non- and -scientific triggers within our article sample.

Lastly, we studied whether the type of news source is correlated to a stigmatizing portrayal of mental health. Figure 5A illustrates that non-scientific sources – which includes the trigger of 'crime' – were significantly more likely to be correlated with a mention of crime in our articles, Fisher's exact test, $p=0.002$). As for destigmatizing elements, scientific news triggers were significantly more likely to

include causes of a mental illness ($\chi^2(1, N=120)=5.434, p=0.02$) and a quote of a mental health expert (Fisher's exact test, $p=0.0000006$) compared to articles that were triggered by non-scientific news. Meanwhile, non-scientific news triggers were significantly more likely to incorporate quotes from individuals with a mental health concern or relative ($\chi^2(1, N=120)=8, p=0.005$) and quotes from celebrities (Fisher's exact test, $p=0.006$). Figure 5B illustrates the correlation of type of news sources with destigmatizing elements.

Fig. 3: Correlations between types of mental illness and frequency of mentioned (de)stigmatizing elements.

(A) Correlation between mental illnesses and frequency of mentioned crimes. Percentages represent the count of mentioned crimes associated with a mental illness divided by the frequency of which a mental illness is mentioned in our article sample. **(B)** Correlation between mental illnesses and frequency of mentioned destigmatizing elements. Percentages represent the count of a destigmatizing element per mentioned mental illness divided by the frequency of which a mental illness is mentioned in our article sample. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, FDR adjusted. PTSD; posttraumatic stress disorder. #; no cause was given for schizophrenia.

Fig.4: Correlations between five types of Dutch newspapers and frequency of mentioned destigmatizing elements around mental health. * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$, FDR adjusted.

Fig. 5: Correlations between types of news triggers and frequency of mentioned (de)stigmatizing elements.

(A) Correlation between news triggers and frequency of mentioned crimes. Percentages represent the count of mentioned crimes associated with a news trigger divided by the frequency of which a news trigger is used in our article sample. **(B)** Correlation between type of news trigger and frequency of mentioned destigmatizing elements. Percentages represent the count of a destigmatizing element per mentioned news trigger divided by the frequency of which a news trigger is used in our article sample. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. #; no quote from a celebrity was mentioned in articles using a scientific news trigger.

Discussion

Stigmatizing portrayal of mental health in general

This study explored the portrayal of mental health in news articles published in five Dutch national newspapers. Previously, a plethora of studies have found a common portrayal of the mentally ill having dangerous and violent attributes (Klin & Lemish, 2008). Our findings demonstrated that one in four of our collected news articles linked a mental health-related topic with the stigmatizing element of crime and violence. Compared to our findings, mental health has both been more frequently linked with violence in Canadian newspapers (Whitley & Wang, 2017) and less frequently in Irish, British and Indian newspapers (Arneaud et al., 2022; Gallagher et al., 2023; Rhydderch et al., 2016). Furthermore, we found that individuals with mental health concerns were predominantly portrayed as perpetrators or suspects of a crime rather than victims in Dutch newspapers, which is in agreement with previous findings elsewhere (Angermeyer & Schulze, 2001; Arneaud et al., 2022). Given together, Dutch newspapers thus spread a biased stance that individuals with mental health conditions are likely to exhibit violent attributes. Consequently, they feed the negative attitude towards mental illnesses by which the general public misleadingly beliefs those with mental health concerns are dangerous and unpredictable. Ultimately, individuals that are indeed experiencing a mental health condition internalize this public stigma, which in turn cascades into negative attitudes towards help-seeking and reduced willingness to seek psychological treatment.

The popular Dutch newspapers *De Telegraaf* and *Algemeen Dagblad* tended to publish more mental health-related articles that were connected to a crime compared to *De Volkskrant*, *NRC* and *Trouw*, although not significantly. Previous Dutch research has distinguished *De Telegraaf* and *Algemeen Dagblad* as popular newspapers, while the latter three newspapers are regarded as high quality newspapers (Roelofs, 2022). British and Irish studies in particular have found a strong significant correlation between popular “tabloid” newspapers and its portrayal of mental health connected to crime and violence (Gallagher et al., 2023; Li et al., 2021). The distinction between popular or “tabloid” newspapers vs. high quality or “broadsheet” newspapers is perceived less clearly within the Netherlands as opposed to other countries, thereby possibly explaining our lack of significance (Legius, 2015). Nevertheless, our finding raises our concern as *De Telegraaf* and *Algemeen Dagblad* are predominantly read by people with a lower level of education than the broadsheet counterparts. Previous literature has highlighted that individuals of lower education are more likely to exhibit a low level mental health literacy and thus a higher tendency to stigmatize those with a mental disorder (Reavley et al., 2012). Hence, the negative portrayal of mental health in popular Dutch newspapers possibly further perpetuates negative attitudes towards mental health among individuals with a low level of education, thereby polarizing stigmatization of mental health within the Dutch population.

Destigmatizing portrayal of mental health in general

Our findings demonstrated that more than half of our studied Dutch news articles included causes for developing a mental health condition. This percentage is higher than found in British and Saudi Arabian newspapers, in which approximately 17% and 28% of the news articles incorporated causes, respectively (Li et al., 2021; McCrae et al., 2019). We believe that Dutch newspapers stimulate the destigmatizing attitude that a mental illness can be developed out of one’s control, instead of blaming one’s personal lack of resilience. We further found that less biological causes were given in comparison to environmental causes, which we argue will again foster a destigmatizing attitude. This reasoning lies in the fact that implementing biological causes of a mental disorder primarily can convey the notion that a mental illness is a fixed genetic state, leading the general public to misleadingly believe a mental illness is a permanent disease (Corrigan et al., 2005; Elliott et al., 2012). As such, individuals with mental health conditions are more likely to exhibit the misinformed attitude that psychological treatment fails

to be beneficial and thus do not seek professional help. On the contrary, the notion that a mental illness can be caused by uncontrollable environmental factors helps audiences to obtain a belief in which mental health conditions can be overcome by mental health interventions.

Forty-two percent of our studied articles mentioned a mental health intervention, which is considerably higher than what has been found in newspapers elsewhere (Chen & Lawrie, 2017; Li et al., 2021). Dutch news articles may thus improve the level of mental health literacy among Dutch audiences. As such, readers are given awareness to different kinds of psychological treatments. Notably, medicines were the most predominantly mentioned mental health intervention in our article sample. Despite the proved effectiveness of medications to treat mental health concerns, previous studies have pinpointed stigmatization towards antidepressants and antipsychotics (Castaldelli-Maia et al., 2011; Jorm, 2000; Jorm et al., 1997). Negative misinformed beliefs towards medication around mental health include its threatening side-effects of lethargy and brain damage, and the perception that those receiving medication are weak and cannot handle emotional problems. Possibly, Dutch newspapers give awareness about medicines that will hamper these attitudes. However, we failed to study the context in which medication was mentioned in our articles. Hence, further investigation is required whether Dutch newspapers indeed discuss mental health-related medication positively to prevent misinformation and stigmatization around this topic.

We further discovered that quotes from mental health experts were incorporated in almost half of our studied articles. This finding is incongruent with other studies, in which roughly 28% of the articles included a quote by a mental health expert in British, Indian and Canadian newspapers (Arneaud et al., 2022; Chen & Lawrie, 2017; Whitley et al., 2015). As Zolezzi *et al.* (2020) states, including quotations from mental health experts provides a degree of validation and trustworthiness to the articles discussing mental health. In turn, readers gain expert knowledge based on scientific evidence that can increase their mental health literacy. In this present study, we did not investigate the content of the quote itself. However, previously it has been shown that expert quotes in mental health-related news articles predominantly exhibit an optimistic and positive tone about mental health (Grandón et al., 2022). Therefore, we deem it likely that the expert quotes within our article sample stimulate positive beliefs and attitudes towards mental health.

Meanwhile, our data indicated that 44% of our articles included a quote by an individual with a mental health concern or a relative. Again, this finding is in disagreement with previous studies; in newspapers elsewhere this percentage lies scarcely between 7% and 37% (Chen & Lawrie, 2017; McCrae et al., 2019; Whitley et al., 2015; Zolezzi et al., 2020). We argue that the emphasis of Dutch newspapers on the perspective of people with a mental illness compared to newspapers elsewhere helps enabling the Dutch population to humanize those with mental illnesses. In this sense, Dutch newspapers more often apply a human interest frame, by which the voices that are heard by those with a mental health concern fosters the perception that people with a mental health concern are real, common and able to speak for themselves. Ultimately, this leads to a decreased stigmatization of mental health within the population. However, our interpretation requires careful consideration as we did not investigate the content of the quote itself.

While the popular Dutch newspapers *De Telegraaf* and *Algemeen Dagblad* tended to publish more mental health-related articles that were connected to the stigmatizing element of crime, our data further uncovered a trend in which the quality newspapers *De Volkskrant*, *NRC* and *Trouw* are more likely to incorporate a quote from a mental health expert and include mental health interventions,

although not significant. This solidifies our assumption that Dutch “broadsheet” newspapers tend to portray mental health in a less stigmatizing manner than “tabloid” newspapers.

The influence of news triggers on portraying mental health

To the best of our knowledge, no studies have explicitly investigated the prevalence of scientific and non-scientific news triggers in newspapers elsewhere. However, Holland (2018) stated that journalists think that readers are not interested in reading scientific advances or ‘breakthroughs’ around mental health as opposed to physical health, as people generally do not believe a mental disorder could happen to them. Therefore, journalists may refrain from writing articles which source is a scientific trigger. In line with this reasoning, our findings revealed that the source that triggers journalists to write mental health-related news articles is more often non-scientific than scientific. Articles originating from a scientific trigger are significantly more likely to include causes of a mental health concern and to incorporate quotations from mental health experts. Hence, we argue that scientific triggers establish objective and trustworthy articles that can improve mental health literacy among its readers and consequently mental health stigma.

Meanwhile, articles stemming from a non-scientific source are significantly more likely to incorporate quotations from an individual with a mental health condition or a relative and from a celebrity. These articles thus apply a human interest frame by which a sympathetic and relatable portrayal of a person with a mental health concern can improve mental health stigma. Given together, we think a balanced combination between news articles rooted from scientific and non-scientific trigger would be beneficial to fight against misinformation and stigmatization around mental health.

Types of mental illnesses and their portrayal

Our findings indicate that different types of mental illnesses are disproportionally represented in Dutch printed newspaper media. As expected, depression was found to be the most commonly featured mental disorder, which is in line with newspapers published elsewhere among which India, UK and Australia (Arneaud et al., 2022; Kenez et al., 2015; Zolezzi et al., 2020). Dutch newspapers predominantly incorporated correct information about depression, having mentioned a large pool of definitions and symptoms with regards to this mental illness according to the DSM-5. Previously, it has been highlighted that the general population tends to have greater awareness of the definitions and symptoms constituting depression in comparison to other mental illnesses (Jorm, 2000). As it therefore likely that journalists have an high inherent level of depression literacy, we propose that there is a positive interplay between printed media and society in strengthening the mental health literacy of depression among the population. In line with our assumption that depression literacy is high among journalists, we found that depression was least frequently connected with crime and substance. Indeed, mental health literacy has previously been linked with decreased stigmatizing attitudes towards a mental illness.

Despite the higher prevalence of anxiety disorders in comparison to depression among the Dutch population, 15% vs. 12% as of 2022, anxiety disorder was only the third-most commonly mentioned mental disorder (Trimbos Instituut, 2023). This finding is in congruence with previous literature that showed that newspaper articles prefer to discuss depressive instead of anxiety mental conditions (Arneaud et al., 2022; Kenez et al., 2015; Zolezzi et al., 2020). Previous research has highlighted a low anxiety literacy, by which individuals have difficulty in recognizing symptoms of anxiety disorder (Altweck et al., 2015). Additionally, as anxiety disorder is often failed to be recognized, individuals are unlikely to obtain knowledge regarding suitable interventions and to seek treatment. Therefore, we deem it crucial to give correct and elaborate information about anxiety disorder in the form of printed

media. To our concern, anxiety disorders were only scarcely described or defined in our analysed articles. The symptoms given for anxiety disorder predominantly involved physical concerns including sweating and shaking, which are not regarded as a DSM-5 criteria for this mental illness. Also, causes, quotes of experts and mental health interventions were not more frequently mentioned when discussing anxiety compared to other mental diseases, despite the necessity to improve anxiety literacy and help-seeking in our population.

In our last remark about depression and anxiety disorder, we emphasize our concern regarding overlap between symptomatology of the diseases. While depression literacy is presumably high among the population, it has previously been indicated that depression and its symptoms are mistakenly overgeneralized (Reavley & Jorm, 2012). Consequently, it is likely hard for individuals to differentiate depression with other mental illnesses. This reasoning may explain the low prevalence of mentioned anxiety disorder in our article sample, as journalists incorrectly place it under the umbrella of depression. Also, depression was incorrectly labeled as *having anxious thoughts* in our article sample, thereby preventing anxiety disorder to be perceived as a sole mental disorder. Consequently, this current portrayal in Dutch newspapers spreads misinformation of depression and anxiety disorder, by which anxiety disorder could be incorrectly recognized as depression and vice versa.

To our knowledge, this present study is the first to explore the position of burn-out relative to other featured mental disorders in newspapers. The concept of burn-out emerged over 35 years ago and quickly gained global significance (Schaufeli et al., 2009). However, this mental health condition is only considered a disorder as of 2019 by ICD-11, thereby being excluded from content analyses into newspapers before this date. Our findings demonstrated that burn-out was the second most featured mental disorder discussed in our article sample. While burn-out has been described by a variety of symptoms as described by ICD-11 in our article sample, we noticed that articles occasionally described burn-out incorrectly. To our knowledge, no studies as of yet have specifically investigated burnout literacy in the general population. However, unclarity exists regarding the definition of burn-out by which some argue that the concept of burn-out largely overlaps other mental illnesses including depression (Durand-Moreau, 2019). In line with this argumentation, we found that burn-out was frequently misleadingly described as *feeling depressed or anxious*, which in reality describes depression and anxiety disorder, respectively. Hence, we argue that news journalists further stimulate the varying conceptualization of burnout, thereby lowering burnout literacy within the Dutch population.

Given that burnout literacy is presumably low within the population, it could be expected that journalists lack the knowledge of mental health interventions applicable for treating burnout. In congruence with this expectation, we found that articles mentioning burn-out were less likely to include mental health interventions compared to articles mentioning others mental illnesses including depression and (C)PTSD. Limited research has been devoted to investigate stigmatizing stances towards burn-out. May et al. (2020) argued that burn-out is perceived as a stigmatized condition in a sense that it is the individual's own fault for developing a burn-out. On the other hand, burn-out can be regarded as an indicator of success as it oftentimes develops due to hard-working characteristics (Röhm et al., 2022). In line with the latter studies, our findings did not indicate that burn-out was more likely to be portrayed as a consequence of the lack of an individual's resilience.

The incongruency between the study by May and colleagues and our findings could be due to a media hype that conquered the Netherlands during the timespan of our article selection: culture of fear (*Dutch: angstcultuur*) in Dutch workplaces. Most notably, it was brought forward that the well-known Dutch talk show *De Wereld Draait Door* cultivated a place of fear, by which its employers experienced

intimidation and humiliation by those higher up which led to high numbers of burn-out. Media attention regarding this topic skyrocketed, by which those suffering from toxic workplaces were portrayed as victims. Hence, the general population recognized that burn-out can be developed by unhealthy work environments, rather than one's lack of resilience. Consequently, this could be a possibility on why burn-out is not particularly portrayed in a stigmatizing manner in our article sample.

We found no significant differences in the degree to which different mental illnesses are portrayed in a stigmatizing manner. However, a trend was revealed by which personality disorder and schizophrenia were more stigmatized than others in terms of their connection to a crime. This pattern is in congruence with a recent study, in which it was found that severe mental illnesses were more likely featured in stigmatizing news articles compared to common mental disorders (Li et al., 2021; Rhydderch et al., 2016). Against our expectations however, schizophrenia was rarely mentioned in Dutch newspapers, contradicting our expectations as this mental illness has been covered disproportionately well in news articles elsewhere (Arneaud et al., 2022; Gallagher et al., 2023). However, given together, Dutch newspapers tend to further perpetuate stigma regarding psychiatric disorders, which will only worsen the already detected low psychiatric literacy in society (Furnham & Wineslaus, 2012).

Surprisingly, (C)PTSD was elaborately and precisely defined and described in our article sample according to DSM-5. Previously, a study by Lee, Furnham and Merritt (Lee et al., 2017) argued that (C)PTSD is in fact under-recognized among the general population and is met with a low mental health literacy score. This holds especially true when (C)PTSD is caused by sexual assault and indirect trauma exposure as opposed to military combat or man-made disasters. Meanwhile, mental health literacy of (C)PTSD is found to be inversely correlated with internalized stigma and negative attitudes towards mental health interventions (Williston & Vogt, 2022). Therefore, the elaborate and correct knowledge that our studied news articles transfers to the Dutch population may improve mental health literacy of (C)PTSD and thus attitudes towards help-seeking and public stigma.

Limitations

This present study is not without limitations. Only articles from printed newspapers were taken into consideration, thereby excluding online newspaper articles. Recent numbers however, reveal that Dutch newspapers reach a lot of young adults through online platforms (Grimm, 2022b). Nevertheless, we argue that printed articles are most likely also made available online and vice versa. Notably, readers online have to pay subscription fees in order to read articles on the websites of our studied newspapers. In the Netherlands however, audiences can also read free online news sources such as NU.nl, Metro.nl and NOS.nl. To obtain a complete overview of news media and its portrayal in mental health within the Netherlands, we therefore advice future studies to incorporate both printed, online and free news sources in their investigation.

As opposed to content analyses on news articles around the topic of mental health elsewhere, news articles in this study were not directly coded as stigmatizing or destigmatizing. We experienced this former distinction as rather subjective, since articles could incorporate both stigmatizing and destigmatizing elements and thus could jeopardize interrater reliability. It was therefore decided to code the (de)stigmatizing nature of the article by assessing its (de)stigmatizing elements separately. On the downside however, no overall stigmatization 'score' could be achieved per article without transforming our data. Therefore, more sophisticated statistical analyses such as a logistic regression were deemed inappropriate due to a lack of robustness. Likewise, qualitative data was not coded as stigmatizing and destigmatizing due to subjectivity. As already touched upon briefly, any information on latent context within the news articles is therefore missing. Hence, we suggest future studies to

focus on qualitative data and its context within Dutch news articles to establish whether quotations and mental health interventions are placed in a positive or negative light.

Finally, our relative short search period of 10 weeks, which resulted in a total of 120 news articles to be analyzed, could be regarded as a limitation. Especially several types of mental illnesses, among which schizophrenia, were only mentioned scarcely in our article sample. While schizophrenia was expected to be particularly portrayed in a stigmatizing manner, we failed to detect a significant correlation. However, as we saw some promising trends, a larger article sample in future studies could solidify these patterns into significant results.

Conclusion and implications

While similar studies have been performed in newspapers elsewhere, to our knowledge this study is the first to step into the unknown terrain of how mental health is portrayed in the printed media of the Netherlands. Meanwhile, as opposed to previous research, this present study is one of the few that analyzes the topic of mental health in news articles published after the height of the COVID-19 pandemic, by which mental health condition within the Dutch population has reportedly worsened. In line with newspapers elsewhere, this study found that Dutch newspapers tend to spread a biased stance that individuals with mental health conditions, in particular those with a psychiatric disorder, are likely to exhibit violent attributes. However, Dutch newspapers also frequently incorporate destigmatizing elements, including causes of mental health conditions, quotations by experts or individuals with a mental health concern or relative, and mental health interventions.

Dutch newspapers portray mental health in a destigmatizing manner relative to newspapers elsewhere, yet there is considerable room for improvement. For ten years, the Dutch anti-stigma organization *Samen Sterk Zonder Stigma* aimed to educate journalists on how to avoid writing stigmatizing articles regarding mental health (Samen Sterk Zonder Stigma, n.d.). As of 2021, the organization ceased to exist due to lack of subsidy received. Given our current findings however, journalists still need guidance and education on how to write about mental health. While Dutch guidelines on reporting suicide exist, our study highlights that the guidelines should extend to mental health in general.

Anti-stigma campaigns *Time to Change* in the UK and *Mindframe* in Australia are at the forefront in providing tools and interventions for journalists for how to portray mental health (Mind, n.d.; Mindframe, n.d.). While their guidelines tackle stigmatization of mental health in printed media, our findings uncovered that attention should also be given to improving mental health literacy among journalists. Dutch newspapers tend to misinform its readers regarding symptomatology of depression, anxiety disorder and burn-out. As such, the general population is likely to have more difficulty in recognizing a mental illness, thereby delaying the search for professional help. By establishing unique guidelines and workshops incorporating both stigma and mental health literacy as its components, journalists are guided to communicate correctly and objectively about mental health. Consequently, these tools could create a uniform portrayal of mental health among both popular and quality newspapers. As a result, polarization is weakened by which all facets of our population are well-informed about mental health. Ultimately, newspapers may then have the power to increase willingness to seek psychological help among the population and therefore to fight the modern epidemic of poor mental health.

References

- Adlaf, E. M., Hamilton, H. A., Wu, F., & Noh, S. (2009). Adolescent stigma towards drug addiction: Effects of age and drug use behaviour. *Addictive Behaviors, 34*(4), 360–364.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addbeh.2008.11.012>
- Altheide, D. L., & Schneider, C. J. (2013). *Qualitative Media Analysis*. SAGE Publications, Ltd.
<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781452270043>
- Altweck, L., Marshall, T. C., Ferenczi, N., & Lefringhausen, K. (2015). Mental health literacy: A cross-cultural approach to knowledge and beliefs about depression, schizophrenia and generalized anxiety disorder. *Frontiers in Psychology, 6*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.01272>
- American Psychiatric Association, & American Psychiatric Association (Eds.). (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders: DSM-5* (5th ed). American Psychiatric Association.
- Angermeyer, M. C., & Schulze, B. (2001). Reinforcing stereotypes: How the focus on forensic cases in news reporting may influence public attitudes towards the mentally ill. *International Journal of Law and Psychiatry, 24*(4–5), 469–486. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0160-2527\(01\)00079-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0160-2527(01)00079-6)
- Arneaud, G. J., Kar, A., Majumder, S., Molodynski, A., Lovett, K., & Kar, S. (2022). Mental health disorders in English newspapers of India: A retrospective study. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00207640221132426>
- Brooks, S. K., Webster, R. K., Smith, L. E., Woodland, L., Wessely, S., Greenberg, N., & Rubin, G. J. (2020). The psychological impact of quarantine and how to reduce it: Rapid review of the evidence. *The Lancet, 395*(10227), 912–920. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30460-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30460-8)
- Burns, S., Tapsell, A., Perlman, D., Patterson, C., & Moxham, L. (2022). Stigma in the media: Investigating journalism students attitudes towards mental illness. *International Journal of Mental Health Nursing, 31*(1), 104–110. <https://doi.org/10.1111/inm.12941>
- Campbell, J. L., Quincy, C., Osserman, J., & Pedersen, O. K. (2013). Coding In-depth Semistructured Interviews: Problems of Unitization and Intercoder Reliability and Agreement. *Sociological Methods & Research, 42*(3), 294–320. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0049124113500475>
- Castaldelli-Maia, J. M., Scomarini, L. B., Andrade, A. G. D., Bhugra, D., De Toledo Ferraz Alves, T. C., & D’Elia, G. (2011). Perceptions of and Attitudes Toward Antidepressants: Stigma Attached to Their Use-A Review. *Journal of Nervous & Mental Disease, 199*(11), 866–871.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/NMD.0b013e3182388950>
- Chen, M., & Lawrie, S. (2017). Newspaper depictions of mental and physical health. *BJPsych Bulletin, 41*(6), 308–313. <https://doi.org/10.1192/pb.bp.116.054775>
- Clement, S., Schauman, O., Graham, T., Maggioni, F., Evans-Lacko, S., Bezborodovs, N., Morgan, C., Rüsç, N., Brown, J. S. L., & Thornicroft, G. (2015). What is the impact of mental health-

- related stigma on help-seeking? A systematic review of quantitative and qualitative studies. *Psychological Medicine*, 45(1), 11–27. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291714000129>
- Corrigan, P. W., & Watson, A. C. (2002). Understanding the impact of stigma on people with mental illness. *World Psychiatry: Official Journal of the World Psychiatric Association (WPA)*, 1(1), 16–20.
- Corrigan, P. W., Watson, A. C., Gracia, G., Slopen, N., Rasinski, K., & Hall, L. L. (2005). Newspaper stories as measures of structural stigma. *Psychiatric Services (Washington, D.C.)*, 56(5), 551–556. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ps.56.5.551>
- Durand-Moreau, Q. V. (2019). Is burn-out finally a disease or not? *Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 76(12), 938–938. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oemed-2019-106094>
- Elliott, M., Maitoza, R., & Schwinger, E. (2012). Subjective accounts of the causes of mental illness in the USA. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 58(6), 562–567. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020764011415207>
- Encarnación Villalba Babiloni, T. (2016). Madness as Psychosocial Function in the Ancient Myth of Heracles. *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, VIII(1).
- Friedman, L. D. (Ed.). (2020). Stop the Presses: Journalistic Treatment of Mental Illness. In J. M. Metzler, A. L. Caplan, J. Turow, & O. F. Wahl, *Cultural Sutures* (pp. 55–70). Duke University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9780822385530-005>
- Furnham, A., & Wincelous, J. (2012). Psychiatric Literacy and the Personality Disorders. *Psychopathology*, 45(1), 29–41. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000325885>
- Gaebel, W., Rössler, W., & Sartorius, N. (Eds.). (2017). *The Stigma of Mental Illness—End of the Story?* Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-27839-1>
- Gallagher, M., O’Leary, C., McGreal-Ballone, A., & Duffy, R. (2023). The portrayal of mental health in Irish mainstream news media. *The International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 69(2), 467–475. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00207640221111756>
- Goffman, E. (1963). *Stigma: Notes on the management of spoiled identity*. Simon & Schuster, Inc.
- Grandón, P., Fernández Vega, D., Sánchez Oñate, A. A., Vielma Aguilera, A. V., Villagrán Valenzuela, L., Vidal Gutiérrez, D., Inostroza Rovengno, C., & Whitley, R. (2022). Mental disorders in the media: A retrospective study of newspaper coverage in the Chilean Press. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 68(7), 1351–1362. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00207640211023086>
- Grimm, E. (2020). *Bereik gedrukte dagbladen houdt stand*. <https://www.ndpnieuwsmedia.nl/2020/01/09/bereik-gedrukte-dagbladen-houdt-stand/>
- Grimm, E. (2022a). *Dagbladen bereiken met print en online dagelijks miljoenen lezers*. <https://www.ndpnieuwsmedia.nl/2022/09/15/dagbladen-bereiken-met-print-en-online-miljoenen-dagelijkse-lezers/>

- Grimm, E. (2022b). *Groot online bereik zorgt voor verjonging lezerspubliek dagbladmerken*.
<https://www.ndpnieuwsmedia.nl/2022/03/24/groot-online-bereik-zorgt-voor-verjonging-lezerspubliek-dagbladmerken/>
- Hanusch, F. (2013). Sensationalizing death? Graphic disaster images in the tabloid and broadsheet press. *European Journal of Communication*, 28(5), 497–513.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0267323113491349>
- Holland, K. (2018). Making Mental Health News: Australian journalists' views on news values, sources and reporting challenges. *Journalism Studies*, 19(12), 1767–1785.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1461670X.2017.1304826>
- Holman, D. (2015). Exploring the relationship between social class, mental illness stigma and mental health literacy using British national survey data. *Health: An Interdisciplinary Journal for the Social Study of Health, Illness and Medicine*, 19(4), 413–429.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1363459314554316>
- Johansson, S. (2007). *Reading tabloids: Tabloid newspapers and their readers*. Södertörns Högskola.
- Jorm, A. F. (2000). Mental health literacy: Public knowledge and beliefs about mental disorders. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 177(5), 396–401. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.177.5.396>
- Jorm, A. F., Korten, A. E., Jacomb, P. A., Christensen, H., Rodgers, B., & Pollitt, P. (1997). “Mental health literacy”: A survey of the public's ability to recognise mental disorders and their beliefs about the effectiveness of treatment. *Medical Journal of Australia*, 166(4), 182–186.
<https://doi.org/10.5694/j.1326-5377.1997.tb140071.x>
- Jung, H., von Sternberg, K., & Davis, K. (2017). The impact of mental health literacy, stigma, and social support on attitudes toward mental health help-seeking. *International Journal of Mental Health Promotion*, 19(5), 252–267. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14623730.2017.1345687>
- Kenez, S., O'Halloran, P., & Liamputtong, P. (2015). The portrayal of mental health in Australian daily newspapers. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health*, 39(6), 513–517.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/1753-6405.12441>
- Kim, H. C. (2021). Mediating effect of stigma on the relationship between mental health literacy and help-seeking attitudes among university students in South Korea. *International Journal of Mental Health*, 52(2), 163–178. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207411.2021.1965397>
- Klin, A., & Lemish, D. (2008). Mental Disorders Stigma in the Media: Review of Studies on Production, Content, and Influences. *Journal of Health Communication*, 13(5), 434–449.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10810730802198813>
- Kosyluk, K. A., Al-Khouja, M., Bink, A., Buchholz, B., Ellefson, S., Fokuo, K., Goldberg, D., Kraus, D., Leon, A., Michaels, P., Powell, K., Schmidt, A., & Corrigan, P. W. (2016). Challenging the Stigma

- of Mental Illness Among College Students. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 59(3), 325–331.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jadohealth.2016.05.005>
- Krippendorff, K. (1970). Estimating the Reliability, Systematic Error and Random Error of Interval Data. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(1), 61–70.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/001316447003000105>
- Kristensen, S. W., Cramer, J., McCollam, A., Reijnierse, W. G., & Smeets, I. (2021). The matter of complex anti-matter: The portrayal and framing of physics in Dutch newspapers. *Journal of Science Communication*, 20(07), A02. <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.20070202>
- Lee, C. Y., Furnham, A., & Merritt, C. (2017). Effect of directness of exposure and trauma type on Mental Health Literacy of PTSD. *Journal of Mental Health*, 26(3), 257–263.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09638237.2016.1276531>
- Legius, R. (2015). *One More Thing: Een discoursanalyse van de verwachtingen rondom de Apple Watch in de Nederlandse kranten*. Universiteit Utrecht.
- Li, Y., Hildersley, R., Ho, G. W. K., Potts, L., & Henderson, C. (2021). Relationships between types of UK national newspapers, illness classification, and stigmatising coverage of mental disorders. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 56(9), 1527–1535.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-021-02027-7>
- Masinga, N., Nyamaruze, P., & Akintola, O. (2022). A retrospective study exploring how South African newspapers framed Schizophrenia and other psychotic disorders over an 11-year period (2004-2014). *BMC Psychiatry*, 22(1), 667. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-022-04276-5>
- May, R. W., Terman, J. M., Foster, G., Seibert, G. S., & Fincham, F. D. (2020). Burnout Stigma Inventory: Initial Development and Validation in Industry and Academia. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 391. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00391>
- McCrae, N., Sharif, L., & Norman, I. (2019). Media portrayals of mental disorder in Saudi Arabia: A review of popular newspapers. *Transcultural Psychiatry*, 56(2), 428–442.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1363461518819117>
- McGinty, E. E., Presskreischer, R., Han, H., & Barry, C. L. (2020). Psychological Distress and Loneliness Reported by US Adults in 2018 and April 2020. *JAMA*, 324(1), 93.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.9740>
- McHugh, M. L. (2013). The Chi-square test of independence. *Biochemia Medica*, 143–149.
<https://doi.org/10.11613/BM.2013.018>
- Mental Health America. (2022). *State of Mental Health in America*.
[https://mhanational.org/issues/2022/mental-health-america-adult-data#:~:text=Adult%20Prevalence%20of%20Mental%20Illness%20\(AMI\)%202022&text=19.8%25%20of%20adults%20are%20experiencing,Jersey%20to%2026.86%25%20in%20Utah.](https://mhanational.org/issues/2022/mental-health-america-adult-data#:~:text=Adult%20Prevalence%20of%20Mental%20Illness%20(AMI)%202022&text=19.8%25%20of%20adults%20are%20experiencing,Jersey%20to%2026.86%25%20in%20Utah.)

- Milin, R., Kutcher, S., Lewis, S. P., Walker, S., Wei, Y., Ferrill, N., & Armstrong, M. A. (2016). Impact of a Mental Health Curriculum on Knowledge and Stigma Among High School Students: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry, 55*(5), 383-391.e1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2016.02.018>
- Miller, A. N., Napakol, A., & Kujak, M. K. (2020). Representation of Mental Illness in Leading Ugandan Daily Newspapers: A Content Analysis. *Health Communication, 35*(14), 1782–1790. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10410236.2019.1663469>
- Mind. (n.d.). *How to report on mental health*. <https://www.mind.org.uk/media-centre/how-to-report-on-mental-health/>
- Mindframe. (n.d.). *For Media*. <https://mindframe.org.au/industry-hubs/for-media>
- Murphy, N. A., Fatoye, F., & Wibberley, C. (2013). The changing face of newspaper representations of the mentally ill. *Journal of Mental Health (Abingdon, England), 22*(3), 271–282. <https://doi.org/10.3109/09638237.2012.734660>
- Nairn, R. (1999). Does the Use of Psychiatrists as Sources of Information Improve Media Depictions of Mental Illness? A Pilot Study. *Australian & New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry, 33*(4), 583–589. <https://doi.org/10.1080/j.1440-1614.1999.00587.x>
- Nairn, R. G., & Coverdale, J. H. (2005). People Never See Us Living Well: An Appraisal of the Personal Stories About Mental Illness in a Prospective Print Media Sample. *Australian & New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry, 39*(4), 281–287. <https://doi.org/10.1080/j.1440-1614.2005.01566.x>
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *International Journal of Surgery, 88*, 105906. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijssu.2021.105906>
- Pan, K.-Y., Kok, A. A. L., Eikelenboom, M., Horsfall, M., Jörg, F., Luteijn, R. A., Rhebergen, D., Oppen, P. van, Giltay, E. J., & Penninx, B. W. J. H. (2021). The mental health impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on people with and without depressive, anxiety, or obsessive-compulsive disorders: A longitudinal study of three Dutch case-control cohorts. *The Lancet Psychiatry, 8*(2), 121–129. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(20\)30491-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(20)30491-0)
- Phelan, J. C. (2002). Genetic bases of mental illness – a cure for stigma? *Trends in Neurosciences, 25*(8), 430–431. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2236\(02\)02209-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2236(02)02209-9)
- Pierce, M., Hope, H., Ford, T., Hatch, S., Hotopf, M., John, A., Kontopantelis, E., Webb, R., Wessely, S., McManus, S., & Abel, K. M. (2020). Mental health before and during the COVID-19 pandemic: A longitudinal probability sample survey of the UK population. *The Lancet Psychiatry, 7*(10), 883–892. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(20\)30308-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(20)30308-4)

- Reavley, N. J., & Jorm, A. F. (2012). Stigmatising attitudes towards people with mental disorders: Changes in Australia over 8years. *Psychiatry Research*, *197*(3), 302–306.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2012.01.011>
- Reavley, N. J., McCann, T. V., & Jorm, A. F. (2012). Mental health literacy in higher education students: Mental health literacy in higher education students. *Early Intervention in Psychiatry*, *6*(1), 45–52. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-7893.2011.00314.x>
- Rhydderch, D., Krooupa, A. -M., Shefer, G., Goulden, R., Williams, P., Thornicroft, A., Rose, D., Thornicroft, G., & Henderson, C. (2016). Changes in newspaper coverage of mental illness from 2008 to 2014 in England. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, *134*(S446), 45–52.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/acps.12606>
- Richter, D., Wall, A., Bruen, A., & Whittington, R. (2019). Is the global prevalence rate of adult mental illness increasing? Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, *140*(5), 393–407. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acps.13083>
- Roelofs, A. (2022). *Nieuwsframes in persberichten: Een onderzoek naar de waardering van persberichten door journalisten van populaire- en kwaliteitskranten*. Universiteit Utrecht.
- Röhm, A., Nellen, C., Möhring, M., & Hastall, M. R. (2022). Using Comics to Destigmatize Burn-Out and Depression: An Experimental Investigation. *Gesundheitskommunikation in Zeiten Der COVID-19-Pandemie: Beiträge Zur Jahrestagung Der Fachgruppe Gesundheitskommunikation 2021*. <https://doi.org/10.21241/SSOAR.86031>
- Rössler, W. (2016). The stigma of mental disorders: A millennia-long history of social exclusion and prejudices. *EMBO Reports*, *17*(9), 1250–1253. <https://doi.org/10.15252/embr.201643041>
- RStudio Team. (2020). *RStudio: Integrated Development for R* [Computer software]. RStudio.
<http://www.rstudio.com/>
- Samen Sterk Zonder Stigma. (n.d.). <https://samensterkzonderstigma.nl/domein/stigma-in-de-media/>
- Schaufeli, W. B., Leiter, M. P., & Maslach, C. (2009). Burnout: 35 years of research and practice. *Career Development International*, *14*(3), 204–220. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13620430910966406>
- Schnyder, N., Panczak, R., Groth, N., & Schultze-Lutter, F. (2017). Association between mental health-related stigma and active help-seeking: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, *210*(4), 261–268. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.bp.116.189464>
- Sieff, E. (2003). Media frames of mental illnesses: The potential impact of negative frames. *Journal of Mental Health*, *12*(3), 259–269. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0963823031000118249>
- Slopen, N. B., Watson, A. C., Gracia, G., & Corrigan, P. W. (2007). Age Analysis of Newspaper Coverage of Mental Illness. *Journal of Health Communication*, *12*(1), 3–15.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10810730601091292>

- Sønderskov, K. M., Dinesen, P. T., Santini, Z. I., & Østergaard, S. D. (2020). The depressive state of Denmark during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Acta Neuropsychiatrica*, *32*(4), 226–228. <https://doi.org/10.1017/neu.2020.15>
- Stuart, H., Koller, M., Christie, R., & Pietrus, M. (2011). Reducing Mental Health Stigma: A Case Study. *Healthcare Quarterly*, *14*(sp2), 40–49. <https://doi.org/10.12927/hcq.2011.22362>
- Subramanian, R. (2019). Frames of Mental Illness in an Indian Daily Newspaper. *Health Communication*, *34*(14), 1806–1815. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10410236.2018.1536948>
- Taylor, W. L. (1957). Gauging the Mental Health Content of the Mass Media. *Journalism Quarterly*, *34*(2), 191–201. <https://doi.org/10.1177/107769905703400203>
- Trimbos Instituut. (2023). *Aantallen Nederlanders met een 12-maands aandoening*.
- Vogel, D. L., Wade, N. G., & Hackler, A. H. (2007). Perceived public stigma and the willingness to seek counseling: The mediating roles of self-stigma and attitudes toward counseling. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, *54*(1), 40–50. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0167.54.1.40>
- Wahl, O. F. (2003). News Media Portrayal of Mental Illness: Implications for Public Policy. *American Behavioral Scientist*, *46*(12), 1594–1600. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764203254615>
- Wang, C., Pan, R., Wan, X., Tan, Y., Xu, L., Ho, C. S., & Ho, R. C. (2020). Immediate Psychological Responses and Associated Factors during the Initial Stage of the 2019 Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) Epidemic among the General Population in China. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *17*(5), 1729. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17051729>
- Whitley, R., Adeponle, A., & Miller, A. R. (2015). Comparing gendered and generic representations of mental illness in Canadian newspapers: An exploration of the chivalry hypothesis. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, *50*(2), 325–333. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-014-0902-4>
- Whitley, R., & Wang, J. (2017). Good News? A Longitudinal Analysis of Newspaper Portrayals of Mental Illness in Canada 2005 to 2015. *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*, *62*(4), 278–285. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0706743716675856>
- Williston, S. K., & Vogt, D. S. (2022). Mental health literacy in veterans: What do U.S. military veterans know about PTSD and its treatment? *Psychological Services*, *19*(2), 327–334. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ser0000501>
- World Health Organization. (2004). *Promoting Mental Health*. 1–69.
- World Health Organization. (2019a). *International Classification of Diseases, Eleventh Revision (ICD-11)*.
- World Health Organization. (2020). *World Mental Health Day: An opportunity to kick-start a massive scale-up in investment in mental health*. <https://www.who.int/news/item/27-08-2020-world->

mental-health-day-an-opportunity-to-kick-start-a-massive-scale-up-in-investment-in-mental-health#:~:text=Mental%20health%20is%20one%20of,every%2040%20seconds%20by%20suicide.

World Health Organization. (2022). *Schizophrenia*. [https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/schizophrenia#:~:text=Some%20people%20with%20schizophrenia%20experience,worsening%20of%20symptoms%20over%20time.&text=Schizophrenia%20affects%20approximately%2024%20million,300%20people%20\(0.32%25\)%20worldwide](https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/schizophrenia#:~:text=Some%20people%20with%20schizophrenia%20experience,worsening%20of%20symptoms%20over%20time.&text=Schizophrenia%20affects%20approximately%2024%20million,300%20people%20(0.32%25)%20worldwide).

World Health Organization. (2019b). *Mental disorders*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/mental-disorders>

Yates, D., Moore, D., & McGabe, G. (1999). *The Practice of Statistics* (1st ed.). W.H. Freeman.

Zolezzi, M., Elshami, S., & Obaidi, W. (2020). An Exploratory Analysis of the Portrayal of Mental Illness in Qatar's Newspapers. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management, 13*, 1323–1332. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PRBM.S280360>

Supplementary Materials

Table S1: List consulted for developing Dutch search terms

Word	Related word
General terms:	
mentaal	mentale, mentaal welbevinden, mentale gezondheid, mentale gesteldheid, mentale ziekte, mentale aandoening(en)
psychisch	psychische, psychische gezondheid, psychische klacht(en), psychisch probleem (problemen), psychische aandoening(en).
geestelijk(e)	
Terms related to treatment	
therapie	therapeut(e), psychotherapie
psycholoog (psychologe)	psychologisch(e)
psychiatrie	psychiatrisch(e), psychiater, psychische instelling, psychische inrichting.
kliniek	
instelling	
inrichting	
Terms relating to disorders & symptoms	
depressieve stoornis	depressief, depressieve, depressie, somber, moe, lusteloos, burn-out
bipolaire stoornis	bipolair(e), manie, manisch.
angststoornis	bang, angst, paniek, paniekaanval.
obsessieve compulsieve stoornis (OCS)	dwangstoornis, dwangneurose, obsessief.
schizofrene stoornis	Psychoot, psychopaat, psychopathisch(e), psychotisch, schizofreen, schizofrene, schizofrenie, psychose.

Table S2: Interrater reliability scores between two coders for quantitative variables

Categories	Variables	Krippendorff's α	Agreement percentage (%)
Descriptive variables of the article	Day published	0.949	95.8
	Month published	1.000	100
	Newspaper name	1.000	100
	<i>Type article*</i>	0.503	66.7
	Mental health among adolescents/young adults discussed	0.598	87.5
News triggers	News trigger	0.826	91.7
	Scientific news trigger	0.835	91.7
	Non-scientific news trigger	0.72	79.2
	Mental health linked with COVID-19	0.706	91.7
	Mental health as main focus	0.574	79.2
Mental illness classification	Classification of mental illness	0.826	91.7
	Explanation of specified mental illness	0.706	91.7
	Explanation unrelated to specific mental illness	0.449	75
Stigmatization of mental health conditions	Mental health linked with crime	0.466	91.7
	Crime linked with tbs-patient or tbs-clinic	1.000	100
	Role person with mental illness in crime	0.799	91.7
	Mental health linked with substance usage	-0.093	79.2
Destigmatization of mental health conditions	Cause of mental health condition	0.744	87.5
	Biological/genetic cause of mental health condition	0.866	95.8
	Environmental cause of mental health condition	0.732	87.5
	Unspecified cause of mental health condition	0.25	83.3
	Portrayal mental illness as lack of an individual's resilience	0.466	91.7
	Individualized or generic focus	0.826	91.7
	Quote person with mental health condition or relative	0.633	83.3
	Quote politician	-0.0217	91.7
	Quote celebrity	0.654	87.5
	Quote mental health expert	0.755	87.5
	Number quote mental health expert	0.635	75
	Successful recovery	0.753	91.7
	Mental health intervention	0.428	70.8
	Self-treatment tips or tricks	0.726	83.3

Shortage, lack of quality or lack of
visibility of mental healthcare 0.586 79.2

*Data from the variable measuring the type of article was excluded from data analysis due to low intercoder reliability.

Table S3: Interrater reliability between two coders for qualitative data

Categories	Variables	Krippendorff's α	Agreement percentage (%)	Negotiated agreement percentage (%)
Stigmatization of mental health condition	Type of crime	0.496	56	78
	Type of substance abuse	1.000	100	100
Destigmatization of mental health condition	Type of biological cause	1.000	100	100
	Type of environmental cause	0.049	22	100
	Type of mental health intervention	-0.0345	0	75
	Type of self-help behaviour	0.526	60	No agreement met

Table S4: Descriptive variables of article sample in Dutch newspapers

Newspaper	Average word count (range)	Mental health as main focus (N)	Mental health linked with COVID-19 (N)
De Telegraaf	527 (120-1396)	29	4
Algemeen Dagblad	632 (75-2093)	23	4
De Volkskrant	1661 (375-5064)	18	4
NRC	1328 (126-2828)	13	3
Trouw	898 (122-1749)	18	6
Total	943	101	21

Table S5: Prevalence of mental illnesses according to DSM-5 classification in Dutch newspapers

DSM-5 Classification	De Telegraaf		De Volkskrant		NRC	Trouw	Total
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)			
Schizophrenia Spectrum and Other Psychotic Disorders							
Schizophrenia (F20.9)	-	-	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	3 (3)
Bipolar and Related Disorders							
Bipolar disorder (F31)	-	2 (2)	-	-	-	-	2 (2)
Depressive Disorders							
Depression (F32)	3 (3)	7 (6)	10 (8)	11 (9)	11 (9)	11 (9)	42 (35)
Anxiety Disorders							
Anxiety disorder (F40)	1 (<1)	2 (2)	4 (3)	6 (5)	7 (6)	7 (6)	20 (17)
Panic Disorder (F41)	-	-	-	1 (<1)	-	-	1 (<1)
Obsessive-Compulsive and Related Disorders							
Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (F42)	-	1 (<1)	-	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	3(3)
Trauma- and Stressor-Related Disorders							
(Chronic) Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (F43.10)	2 (2)	-	4 (3)	3 (3)	2 (2)	2 (2)	11 (9)
Attachment Disorder (F94)	-	1 (<1)	-	-	-	-	1 (<1)
Somatic Symptom and Related Disorders							
Conversion Disorder (F44)	-	-	1 (<1)	-	-	-	1 (<1)
Feeding and Eating Disorders							
Eating Disorder (F50)	-	-	-	2 (2)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	3 (3)
Anorexia Nervosa (F50)	-	-	-	-	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)
Bulimia Nervosa (F50.2)	1 (<1)	-	-	-	-	-	1 (<1)
Sleep-Wake Disorders							
Nightmare Disorder (F51.5)	-	-	-	1 (<1)	-	-	1 (<1)
Disruptive, Impulse-Control, and Conduct Disorders							
Conduct disorder (F91)	-	1 (<1)	-	-	-	-	1 (<1)
Personality Disorders							
Personality Disorders (F60)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	-	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	4 (3)
Borderline Personality Disorder (F60.3)	-	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	-	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	3(3)
Burn-out*	4 (3)	7 (6)	4 (3)	4 (3)	5 (4)	5 (4)	24 (20)

* Burn-out is not classified as a mental disorder according to the DSM-5 classification. -; indicates 0 (0)

Table S6: Prevalence of symptoms or definitions given per mental illness in Dutch newspapers

Mental illness	De Telegraaf	AD	De Volkskrant	NRC	Trouw	Total
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Schizophrenia	-	-	-	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	2 (2)
Bipolar disorder	-	-	-	-	-	-
Depression	2 (2)	2 (2)	3 (3)	2 (2)	2 (2)	11 (9)
Anxiety disorder	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	-	-	-	2 (2)
Panic Disorder	-	-	-	-	-	-
Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder	-	1 (<1)	-	-	-	1 (<1)
(C)PTSD	1 (<1)	-	3 (3)	2 (2)	-	6 (5)
Attachment Disorder	-	-	-	-	-	-
Conversion Disorder	-	-	1 (<1)	-	-	1 (<1)
Eating Disorder)	-	-	-	1 (<1)	-	1 (<1)
Anorexia Nervosa	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bulimia Nervosa	1 (<1)	-	-	-	-	1 (<1)
Nightmare Disorder	-	-	-	1 (<1)	-	1 (<1)
Conduct disorder	-	-	-	-	-	-
Personality Disorders	-	-	-	-	-	-
Borderline Personality Disorder	-	-	-	-	1 (<1)	1 (<1)
Burn-out	2 (2)	2 (2)	3 (3)	2 (2)	3 (3)	12 (10)

(C)PTSD; (Chronic) Posttraumatic Stress Disorder

Table S7: Prevalence of types of crime and substance abuse in Dutch newspapers

Crime and substance abuse	De Telegraaf	AD	De Volkskrant	NRC	Trouw	Total
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Crime	12 (10)	9 (8)	3 (3)	3 (3)	3 (3)	30 (25)
<i>Perpetrator with mental illness</i>	8 (7)	7 (6)	1 (<1)	3 (3)	2 (2)	21 (18)
Homicide	7 (6)	6 (5)	1 (<1)	2 (2)	1 (<1)	17 (14)
Attempted homicide	7 (6)	4 (3)	-	1 (<1)	-	12 (10)
Verbal or physical violence	-	2 (2)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	-	4 (3)
Sexual assault	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	-	-	1 (<1)	3 (3)
Possession of forbidden objects	-	-	-	-	2 (2)	2 (2)
Other	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	-	-	2 (<1)	4 (3)
<i>Suspect with mental illness</i>	4 (3)	2 (2)	-	-	-	6 (5)
Homicide	3 (3)	2 (2)	-	-	-	5 (4)
Attempted homicide	3 (3)	-	-	-	-	3 (3)
<i>Victim with mental illness</i>	-	-	2 (2)	-	1 (<1)	3 (3)
Sexual assault	-	-	2 (2)	-	1 (<1)	3 (3)
<i>Crime linked with tbs-person or a tbs-clinic</i>	6 (5)	5 (4)	1 (<1)	2 (2)	1 (<1)	15 (13)
Substance abuse	3 (3)	3 (3)	1 (<1)	2 (2)	4 (3)	13 (11)
Drug usage	2 (2)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	3 (3)	8 (7)
Alcohol	-	1 (<1)	-	1 (<1)	4 (2)	6 (5)
Medicine misuse	1 (<1)	2 (2)	-	1 (<1)	-	4 (3)

Table S8: Destigmatizing elements incorporated in Dutch national newspapers

Destigmatizing elements	De Telegraaf	AD	De Volkskrant	NRC	Trouw	Total
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Causes	8 (7)	10 (8)	15 (13)	15 (13)	15 (13)	63 (53)
Environmental	9 (8)	10 (8)	14 (12)	12 (10)	15 (13)	60 (50)
Biological	1 (<1)	3 (3)	5 (4)	5 (4)	2 (2)	16 (13)
Quotes						
Mental health expert	13 (11)	13 (11)	10 (9)	8 (7)	9 (8)	53 (44)
Person with mental health concern or relative	5 (4)	4 (3)	2 (2)	-	3 (3)	14 (12)
Celebrity	2 (2)	7 (6)	4 (3)	4 (3)	3 (3)	20 (17)
Politician	12 (10)	8 (7)	13 (11)	10 (8)	14 (12)	57 (48)
Recovery	4 (3)	5 (4)	7 (6)	5 (4)	5 (4)	26 (22)
Mental health intervention	10 (8)	7 (6)	11 (9)	12 (10)	10 (8)	50 (42)
Self-help behaviour	6 (5)	5 (4)	4 (3)	4 (3)	1 (<1)	20 (17)

Table S9: Prevalence of mentioned biological and environmental causes in Dutch newspapers

Causes	De Telegraaf	AD	De Volkskrant	NRC	Trouw	Total
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Biological	1 (<1)	3 (3)	5 (4)	5 (4)	2 (2)	16 (13)
Genetic predisposition	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	4 (3)	4 (3)	2 (2)	12 (10)
Physical condition	-	2 (2)	-	-	-	2 (2)
Altered microbiota	-	-	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	-	2 (2)
Environmental factors	9 (8)	10 (8)	14 (12)	12 (10)	15 (13)	60 (120)
Stress or trauma/traumatic experiences	4 (3)	5 (4)	7 (6)	8 (7)	7 (6)	31 (26)
Socio-economic factors	4 (3)	3 (3)	4 (3)	3 (3)	5 (4)	19 (16)
Characteristic traits of the individual	3 (3)		2 2 (2)	2 (2)	5 (4)	14 (12)
Early life environment		2 1 (<1)	2 (2)	4 (3)	-	9 (8)
Environmental factors	1 (<1)	-	1 (<1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	7 (6)
Social isolation	-	1 (<1)	2 (2)	1 (<1)	2 (2)	6 (5)
COVID-19 pandemic	1 (<1)	2 (2)	-	-	2 (2)	5 (4)
Technological factors	-	1 (<1)	-	2 (2)	2 (2)	5 (4)
Physical health	-	-	-	1 (<1)	3 (3)	4 (3)

Table S10: Prevalence of types of mentioned mental health interventions in Dutch newspapers

Mental health intervention	De Telegraaf	AD	De Volkskrant	NRC	Trouw	Total
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Medicine	3 (3)	4 (3)	2 (2)	9 (8)	5 (4)	23 (19)
Unspecified therapy	3 (3)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (3)	3 (3)	15 (13)
EMDR	3 (3)	-	2 (2)	-	1 (<1)	6 (5)
Psychotherapy	-	1 (<1)	3 (3)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	6 (5)
Cognitive-behavioral therapy	1 (<1)	-	1 (<1)	2 (2)	-	4 (3)
Processing therapy	1 (<1)	-	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	4 (3)
Activity-based therapy	1 (<1)	-	2 (2)	-	-	3 (3)
Mentoring	-	2 (2)	-	-	1 (<1)	3 (3)
Individual counselling	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	-	-	-	2 (2)
Support group	-	-	1 (<1)	-	1 (<1)	2 (2)
Other	-	-	6 (5)	4 (3)	3 (3)	12 (10)

Table S11: Scientific and non-scientific news triggers in Dutch newspapers

News trigger	De Telegraaf	AD	De Volkskrant	NRC	Trouw	Total
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Scientific	6 (5)	3 (3)	6 (5)	4 (3)	8 (7)	27 (23)
Research that is starting or in progress	-	-	2 (2)	-	-	2 (2)
A new research article, report, scientific book or medical intervention is published or discussed	5 (4)	3 (3)	4 (3)	4 (3)	8 (7)	24 (20)
Other	1 (<1)	-	-	-	-	1 (<1)
Non-scientific	26 (22)	23 (19)	15 (13)	15 (13)	14 (12)	93 (78)
The mental health of a public figure is discussed	1 (<1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	3 (3)	2 (2)	11 (9)
The mental health of an everyday person is discussed	2 (2)	3 (3)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	8 (7)
A political decision or event	3 (3)	3 (3)	1 (<1)	-	1 (<1)	8 (7)
Raising awareness by e.g. a campaign, charity efforts or science communication products	-	2 (2)	2 (2)	-	-	4 (3)
A crime	11 (9)	9 (8)	1 (<1)	2 (2)	1 (<1)	24 (20)
A (public) health concern with no scientific report or study attached	4 (3)	3 (3)	3 (3)	6 (5)	2 (2)	18 (15)
A new initiative, company or business	3 (3)	-	1 (<1)	1 (<1)	3 (3)	8 (7)
Other	2 (2)	1 (<1)	3 (3)	2 (2)	4 (3)	8 (7)

Supplementary Figures

Fig. S1: Frequency of mental illnesses mentioned solely or in combination with other mental illnesses in Dutch newspaper articles. (C)PTSD; (chronic) posttraumatic stress disorder

Fig S2: Prevalence of (de)stigmatizing elements around mental health among types of mental illnesses. (A) The prevalence of stigmatizing elements among types of mental illnesses. * indicates 0% for a type of mental illness. **(B)** The prevalence of destigmatizing elements among types of mental illnesses.

Fig. S3: Prevalence of (de)stigmatizing elements around mental health among five types of Dutch newspapers. (A) The prevalence of stigmatizing elements among Dutch newspapers. * indicates that for *De Volkskrant*, *NRC* and *Trouw* contained no articles attributing mental health to the lack of an individual's resilience. (B) The prevalence of destigmatizing elements among Dutch newspapers.

Supplementary Materials B

Article ID:

Author ID:

1= Coder A (BS)

2= Coder B (LX)

Date:

--/--/----

Descriptive variables of the article

Headline title (copy the title from Nexus Uni).

V5. Name of author (if not known, fill in 0).

V6. On what day of the week was the news article published?

1= Monday

2= Tuesday

3= Wednesday

4= Thursday

5= Friday

6= Saturday

7= Sunday

0= Unclear

V7. In which month was the news article published?

1= October

2= November

3= December

V8. Newspaper Name:

1= De Telegraaf

2= Algemeen Dagblad

3= De Volkskrant

4= NRC

5= Trouw

V10. In which section of the newspaper is the article published (as noted by Nexus Uni)?

V11. Total amount of words of the article in numbers (as noted by Nexis Uni):

V12. Is the article explicitly covering mental health in adolescents and/or young adults?

0= no

1= yes

V13. Which other age group(s) are mentioned and discussed? Please write down. If no other age groups are discussed, write down '0'.

News triggers

V14. What type of event triggered the news article to be written? If there is more than one trigger present, please refer to the first-mentioned and foremost trigger in the text.

- 1= Scientific
- 2= Non-scientific
- 3= Unknown or not clear

If '1', continue to V15 and place '0' at V16. If '2', place '0' at V15 and continue to V16. If '3', place '0' at V15 and V16 and continue to V17.

V15. What kind of scientific event was the cause of writing the article?

- 1= research that is starting or in progress
- 2= a new research article, report, scientific book or medical intervention is published/discussed
- 3= a new research facility studying mental health is opened or built
- 4= an award of grant was rewarded to a researcher
- 5= a scientific conference, talk or lecture about mental health
- 6= other

V16. What kind of non-scientific event was the cause of writing the article?

- 1= the mental health of a public figure (typically in entertainment, sport, science or royalty) is discussed
- 2= the mental health of an everyday person is discussed
- 3= a political decision or event
- 4= raising awareness by e.g. a campaign, charity efforts or science communication products
- 5= a crime
- 6= public (health) concern (issue that affects a large portion of a population) with no report or scientific study attached
- 7= a new initiative, company or business
- 8= other

V17. Is the topic of mental health linked with COVID-19, albeit briefly, in the article?

- 0= no
- 1= yes

V18. Is mental health or a mental health-related topic the main focus of the article? *Mental health or a mental health-related topic is regarded as the main focus if it is mentioned in the first two paragraphs of the article.*

- 0= No
- 1= Yes

Mental illness classification

V19. Is there a specific type of mental illness fully mentioned in the article by its official name according to the DSM-5? Note: here, we define burn-out as a mental illness. (E.g. 'depressive symptoms' does not suffice; it has to be noted as depression).

- 0= no
- 1= yes

If '0', continue to V21.

V20. Which type of mental illness is mentioned in the article? Please write down. If more than one specific mental illness is covered, name all. If nothing is mentioned, please write '0'.

V21. Do they give any explanation of a specific mental illness (e.g. definition, description or symptoms)?

0= no

1= yes

V22. Which symptoms, descriptions or definitions are given for a specific mental illness? Please write these down together with the mental illness. If no symptoms or definitions are clearly mentioned and linked with a specific mental illness, please write '0'

V23. Are there other symptoms or definitions mentioned that are not tied to a specific mental illness in the text?

0= no

1= yes

Stigmatization of mental health conditions

V24. Was a mental health condition (can be either a specified mental illness or not specified) linked with a criminal context?

0= no

1= yes

V25. Was a crime linked to tbs-patient or tbs-clinic?

0= no

1= yes

V26. What was the crime? Please write down. If no crime is mentioned, please write '0'.

V27. What was the role of the person with a mental illness/tbs?

1= victim

2= suspect (not guilty until proven)

3= perpetrator (convicted)

4= other

If not applicable, please write '0'.

V28. Is mental health linked with substance abuse (e.g. nicotine, alcohol, drugs, excess use of pain relievers)?

0= no

1= yes

V29. Which substance(s) are mentioned? Please write down. If applicable, write the type of substance(s) together with the type of mental illness with which they are linked with. If no substances are mentioned, please write '0'.

Destigmatization of mental health conditions

V31. Does the article present causes of a mental illness (either biological, environmental including trauma, or unspecified) in the article?

0= no
1= yes

V32. Did the article mention biological / genetic causes of a mental illness?

0= no
1= yes

V33. Which biological or genetic causes for having a mental illnesses are mentioned? Please write down, together with the corresponding mental illness if applicable. *If no biological / genetic causes are mentioned, please write '0'.*

V34. Did the article mention environmental causes (including trauma) of a mental illness?

0= no
1= yes

V35. Which environmental causes or other for having a mental illness are mentioned? Please write down, together with the corresponding mental illness if applicable. *If no environmental causes are mentioned, please write '0'.*

V38. Is a mental illness portrayed as a consequence of the lack of an individual's resilience?

0= no
1= yes

V39. Is the focus of the news article individualized or generic?

*As Whitley et al. (2015) define, the focus is individualized if the focus of the article is on an individual person with a mental illness (example: *Opnieuw zorgen over mentale gezondheid Britney Spears*). A generic focus implies that mental health is discussed generally.*

1= generic
2= individualized

V40. Does the article contain a direct or paraphrased quote of an person that has/had a mental health condition or a quote from a relative?

0= no
1= yes

V41. Does the article incorporate a direct or paraphrased quote of an politician / one with a political function?

0= no
1= yes

V42. Does the article incorporate a direct or paraphrased quote of a celebrity?

0= no
1= yes

V43. Does the article incorporate a direct or paraphrased quote of an expert(s) in mental health (e.g. therapists, physicians, scientists, spokesperson for mental health-related institute)?

0= no

1= yes

V44. How many different experts in the field of mental health (e.g. therapists, physicians, scientists, spokesperson for mental health-related institute) are quoted or paraphrased in the article? Write down the number. *If no expert is mentioned, write down '0'.*

V45. What type of expert(s) is (are) quoted or paraphrased? (e.g. clinicians, researchers, leaders of mental health organizations). Please write down. If more than one expert is incorporated, write all down. *If no quote by an expert is given, please write '0'.*

V46. Does the article mention successful recovery (for individual person or general) for a mental illness?

0= no

1= yes

V47. Does the article cover possible mental health interventions that are typically prescribed by experts (e.g. therapy, prescription of medicines)?

0= no

1= yes

V48. Which mental health interventions does the article mention that are prescribed and/or held by experts? Please write down. *If not applicable, please write down '0'.*

V49. Does the article cover possible mental health interventions/tips and tricks that one can do themselves (self-help behaviour such as talking about mental health with parents, having a stable daily routine)?

0= no

1= yes

V50. Which mental health interventions/tips and tricks that can do themselves are mentioned in the article? Please write down. *If not applicable, please write down '0'.*

V51. Does the article indicate shortage, lack of quality and/or lack of visibility of mental healthcare in the article?

0= no

1= yes